

D7.2

PLAN FOR THE D & E & C OF RESULTS (PDEC) - UPDATED VERSION

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Abstract

This report provides an updated overview of GRAPHERGIA's D&E&C strategy and related key accomplishments that maximise the outreach and impact of the project's research and innovation. Moreover, it presents GRAPHERGIA's target market analysis, focusing on e-textiles, Li-ion batteries for aerospace and spatial applications, and smart sensors for aviation. With this analysis, GRAPHERGIA's innovation is positioned on these markets, responding to specific customer needs, challenges, gaps and opportunities. It leads the way towards the further definition of the specific exploitation paths for GRAPHERGIA's Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

Keywords

Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation, Market Analysis, Agility, Impact, Sustainability, Awareness, Standardisation, Intellectual Property, E-textiles, Li-Ion Battery, Smart sensors.

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R - Report

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PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

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CO Confidential to GRAPHERGIA project and Commission Services

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ADA	Adamant Composites Ltd.
AUS	AUSTRALO Marketing Lab
Born	Born GmbH - Knitting Engineers
ComS	ComSensus
CRM	Critical Raw Materials
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR e.V.)
ESPR	Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation
FORTH	Foundation For Research and Technology Hellas (Project coordinator)
Gfi	GRAPHENE Flagship Initiative
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IRG	Industrial Reference Group
KER	Key Exploitable Result
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life cycle costing
Li-ion	Lithium Ion (electrochemical cells)
NTT	Next Technology Tecnotessile
PLE	Pleione Energy GmbH
PE CVD	Plasma-Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition process.
R2R	Roll-to-roll (manufacturing process)
SLCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
TENG	Triboelectric nano-generator
UGE	University of Gustave Eiffel / ESYCOM lab
URM	University "Sapienza" Rome
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides a comprehensive analysis of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities carried out in the GRAPHERGIA project from M6 (March 2024) to M26 (November 2025). It is a follow-up to the previous report, Deliverable 7.1, that established the overall impact strategy and initiated the first activities. The central aim is to **sustain the impact of the scientific and technological results achieved by developing novel laser-assisted pilot lines for graphene-based energy-harvesting and storage solutions.**

Stakeholder engagement focuses on working with target stakeholders to establish collaborations and opportunities to exchange best practices. The **GRAPHERGIA hub** is at the nexus of innovations in smart textiles, next-gen Li-ion batteries and 2D materials, and today it **gathers 75 members**. It has offered **three webinars** to stakeholders. In addition, GRAPHERGIA is an active member of the Graphene Flagship initiative, contributing to several key working groups and having **run 13 collaboration actions** that have enabled ongoing research and innovation.

Communication is dedicated to raising public awareness among target stakeholders about GRAPHERGIA activities and results. It follows a clear, defined strategy from the start and adapts to the project's progress and milestones. **The progress is smooth; the GRAPHERGIA website records 15K+ visitors, the social media channels count 2K+ followers, and the newsletter has 590+ followers.** The communication content regularly presents GRAPHERGIA's scientific approach (e.g., methodologies, involved researchers, and objectives), its ongoing activities (workshops, webinars and stakeholder events) and results (deliverables and scientific publications).

Dissemination focuses on enabling the stakeholders to use the project's open results. Therefore, awareness articles, scientific publications and events are essential building blocks for this. Now, **the GRAPHERGIA project has published 10 scientific papers, participated in 21 events and (co-) hosted 8 workshops.** These activities have created new connections with stakeholders from Europe and beyond, including the United States, Canada, Japan, and South Korea.

Exploitation enables the project's innovation results and impact to be sustained beyond its lifetime. The consortium has defined the set of **eight key exploitable results** in their IPR background and foreground, and their **exploitation plans, either individual or joint**, are further agreed upon in a series of internal exploitation workshops. ***This is the public version of the submitted deliverable. For IPR reasons, it does not include any sensitive information related to GRAPHERGIA's KERs, which are shared only with the European Commission at the moment.*** Moreover, the GRAPHERGIA team has conducted target market insights analysis across **three key sectors: smart textiles, Li-ion batteries, and smart sensors for aviation.**

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Management focuses on providing the necessary support for the resulting innovation management, beyond the project duration. GRAPHERGIA's Deliverable 7.4 'Preliminary IPR management and Exploitation Plan' sets the strategy for the IPR management. As the research activities have progressed and the exploitation potential of the result can be better foreseen, the consortium has started discussing the potential **resulting patents, with patent landscape analysis and internal agreements to be managed in the coming months.**

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1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is the second in a series of three GRAPHERGIA deliverables (7.1, 7.2, and 7.3) that provide a clear overview of the project's communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. These sit under the Work Package 7 “Dissemination, exploitation and communication of the project results”, led by AUS.

1.1 Structure of the report

The report consists of five sections, but all the topics discussed are interrelated, each of them contributing to foster the impact and sustainability of the GRAPHERGIA Project:

- **Section 2** shares the updates of the GRAPHERGIA's **community building** activities, including the GRAPHERGIA Hub and the Graphene Flagship initiative.
- **Section 3** presents the activities and initial results in **communication**.
- **Section 4** shows the project's performance in **dissemination**.
- **Section 5** is focused on the **exploitation** of GRAPHERGIA's key results.
- **Section 6** shares **the conclusions and the next steps** for the impact activities of the project.

1.2 Update of the related tasks and deliverables

This deliverable, offering an overarching strategy for GRAPHERGIA dissemination, communication and exploitation, is published as part of the WP7 tasks:

- T7.1 Dissemination and Communication
- T7.2 Exploitation plan and Project sustainability
- T7.3 IPR Management
- T7.4 Clustering activities and community building

In line with these tasks, the report is linked to the following approved reports:

D7.1 Plan for the D&E&C Results – First version (M6, AUS): sets the overall framework, objectives and timeline for DEC activities for GRAPHERGIA.

D7.4 Preliminary IPR and exploitation plan (M12, EUGL). It will provide the outline of the IPR management cycles for the GRAPHERGIA innovation and link the IPR management to the general exploitation plan.

In line with these tasks, the report is linked to forthcoming deliverables of the WP7, including

- **D7.3 Plan for the D&E&C Results - Final version** (M42, AUS). It will provide the related results from the second project half, as well as provide lessons learnt and insights into plans to sustain the results beyond the project duration.
- **D7.5 Final IPR and exploitation plan** (M42, EUGL). It will showcase the results of the IPR management strategy and its impact on the overall exploitation plan.
- **D7.6 GRAPHERGIA Best practices handbook** (M42, AUS). It aims to disseminate the acquired know-how and experience through research collaborations with international graphene, smart textiles, and battery communities. It will showcase the most meaningful results from the collaboration with the Graphene Flagship initiative, encouraging synergies with other related initiatives. It will also share the most relevant findings related to standardisation, regulations, and innovation road mapping.

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2 COMMUNITY BUILDING UPDATES

Deliverable 7.1 provides the definition and key categories of GRAPHERGIA’s target stakeholders who are in the centre of all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities of the project. These stakeholders are also part of the project’s community-building activities. During the 1st project half, until M26 (November 2025), the project established the “GRAPHERGIA Hub”, a platform for knowledge exchange and collaboration, and it has initiated several fruitful collaborations with the Graphene Flagship ecosystem.

2.1 GRAPHERGIA Hub

GRAPHERGIA is at the nexus of three domains that are innovating energy solutions for tomorrow. It connects the dots between graphene innovation, advances in smart textiles, and next-generation sustainable battery technologies. GRAPHERGIA Hub was launched in January 2025 to provide a platform for collaboration across the specified sectors, with its first activity (such as an IPR webinar) held shortly after its release. Ultimately, our hub aims to provide a platform for research and innovation (R&I) and related initiatives; this collaboration results in faster R&I progress, better resource use, and greater societal impact.

Figure 1: The GRAPHERGIA Hub visual

Today, the hub has 75 individual members who have agreed to board the hub and have joined the GRAPHERGIA webinars. These members benefit from:

- A platform for connections and collaborations with experts and pioneers in graphene technology, smart textiles, and sustainable batteries.

- Access to webinars, joint workshops, and joint meetings to promote innovation and share best practices.
- Opportunities to co-author publications and collaborate in funding activities.

2.1.1 Webinars

GRAPHERGIA Hub has offered three webinars to the community, gathering 138 registrations. The IPR webinar was open only to the project and the GF*i* community, whereas the two other webinars were open to all interested stakeholders. Moreover, GRAPHERGIA website (graphergia.eu) includes a page that openly shares all resources from the public webinar sessions: <https://graphergia.eu/webinars/>.

The GRAPHERGIA team is actively connecting with sister projects and new collaborations to identify joint areas of interest that could be topics for new webinar sessions.

Figure 2: Capture from GRAPHERGIA Webinar

Table 1: The GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinars

Date	Title	More information
13-Nov-25	GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinar Series 3 - Laser-Induced Graphene & MXenes on Polymer Substrates for Wearable Devices	https://graphergia.eu/2025/11/13/graphergia-hub-webinar-series-3-laser-induced-graphene-mxenes-for-wearable-devices-a-remarkable-session/
28-Mar-25	GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinar Series 2 - Sustainability Assessment and Eco-Design for Graphene-Based Products	https://graphergia.eu/2025/03/17/graphergia-hub-invites-you-to-their-webinar-on-sustainability-assessment-eco-design-for-graphene-based-products/
30-Jan-25	GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinar Series 1 - IPR Management	https://graphergia.eu/2025/01/30/graphergia-hub-presents-our-first-webinar-dedicated-to-ipr-management/

2.1.2 Resource library

As part of the Hub activities and in line with the principle of open research, GRAPHERGIA ensures all public scientific results are shared across its communication channels in an easily accessible and timely manner. For this, the hub offers a dedicated web page: <https://graphergia.eu/graphergia-hub-resources/>

2.1.3 Community of exchange

For the moment, 58 organisations from 28 countries worldwide active in GRAPHERGIA's action fields are represented in the Hub. Beyond future online information sharing sessions, the project's aim is to leverage this community of exchange in its research activities, such as gathering responses to the SLCA survey (WP6), or feedback on the exploitation opportunities (WP7).

Table 2: Organisations represented in the GRAPHERGIA Hub

Organisation	Country
Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology	Australia
UFABC	Brazil
UCT Prague	Czech Republic
UJEP	CZ
Palacky University Olomouc, CATRIN	CZ
Evnia	Denmark
Beneq	Finland
Tampere University	Finland
University of Tampere	Finland
GRAPHENE PRODUCTION	France
IHP GmbH	Germany
EurA AG	Germany
Fraunhofer Institute for Chemical Technology ICT	Germany
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Greece
University of Patras	Greece
Q-PLAN International	Greece
AMIRES	Hungary
Indian Institute of Space Science and Technology, Thiruvananthapuram	India
IIT Madras	India
Iisc	India
BL Graphene	India
Bhargavi Labs	India
TACC LTD	India
IITG	India
Institute of Chemical Technology Mumbai	India

Trinity College Dublin	Ireland
Nexiam	Italy
Iris SRL	Italy
Nano prom	Italy
CNR	Italy
The National Center for Physical Sciences and Technology	Lithuania
SCME NUST	Pakistan
Azygos Global Technology Pvt Ltd	Pakistan
Lukasiewicz Research Network - Poznan Institute of Technology	Poland
Skolkovo Institute of Science and Technology	Russia
King Abdullah Ursity of Science and Technology	Saudi Arabia
Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade	Serbia
Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade	Serbia
University of Novi Sad	Serbia
ICTM	Serbia
Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy	Serbia
University of Ljubljana	Slovenia
ICN2	Spain
Graphenea	Spain
AIMEN Technology Center	Spain
Torreced SA	Spain
Eurecat	Spain
Csic	Spain
RISE	Sweden
Hacettepe University	TR
National Institute of Research and Physicochemical Analysis	Tunisia
Grafenbiotech Nanotechnology Inc.	Turkey
Sabancı University SUNUM	Turkey
Boeing	Turkey
POLYTEKS TEKSTİL SAN ARAŞ VE EĞT A.Ş.	Turkey
Khalifa University	United Arab Emirates
Baugh Tech Energy	US
Central West	US

2.2 Graphene Flagship initiative

GRAPHERGIA is part of the [Graphene Flagship initiative](#), which works to advance technologies that rely on graphene and other 2-dimension (2D) materials.

2.2.1 Key activities within GFi

To kick off this tight collaboration with the Graphene Flagship Initiative (GFi), FORTH, AUS, ADA and PLE participated in the Graphene Flagship Initiative kick-off meeting hosted in Gothenburg (Sweden) on February 5- 6, 2024. This was a great opportunity to meet the sister project representatives and begin connecting with them to plan joint activities. A dedicated post-event article was shared on GRAPHERGIA channels.

The Gfi ties 12 sibling projects focused on different innovation areas in graphene. GRAPHERGIA is an active member of this innovation ecosystem, and it's constantly engaged in running activities and working groups (WG), including notably:

- **Project managers' network WG:** FORTH represents GRAPHERGIA in this group that aims to harmonise the coordination and planning of the sibling projects, and the collaboration of the sibling projects with Graphene Flagship. This group has had 9 meetings and 3 workshops so far. GRAPHERGIA is also contributing to the GFi effort to unify some common KPIs between the GF projects.
- **Coordination Board WG:** FORTH represents GRAPHERGIA in this group, engaging all GFi projects' coordinators to ensure a common governance structure of the ecosystem. This group has met 12 times so far.
- **Innovation WG:** PLE and BORN represent GRAPHERGIA in this working group, which works to bridge the gap between research to industry and market.
- **Dissemination WG:** AUS represents GRAPHERGIA in this group that oversees the communication and dissemination of the sister projects. This collaboration enables us to plan cross-project communication campaigns, for instance to promote key results and events as well as putting in place joint dissemination activities, such workshops. This group gathers online every two months.
- **Roadmapping WG:** ADA represents GRAPHERGIA in this group that focuses on defining value chains for the innovation and technologies resulting from the project, which supports the commercialization beyond the project. The group has been convened 4 times so far.
- **Standardisation WG:** FORTH represents GRAPHERGIA in this group that contributes to the industrialisation support that GFi offers to the projects. The working group offers training and guidelines for standardisation and regulation.
- **National thematic representatives WG:** FORTH represents GRAPHERGIA in this working group.
- **Graphene Flagship Ambassadors:** FORTH represents GRAPHERGIA in this activity.

- **REACH/ECHA Committee:** FORTH represents GRAPHERGIA in this committee, working on the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals / European Chemical Agency. The committee has met 3 times so far.
- **Associated members (AM) / Partnering Projects (PP):** GRAPHERGIA has contributed to the [Association Mechanism of Graphene Flagship](#) introducing the following members and projects:
 - The POLYGRAPH project (PP), EU ([link](#))
 - The EMPHASIS project (PP), EU ([link](#))
 - The University of Belgrade (AM), Serbia ([link](#))
 - Solvionic, France (AM) ([link](#))
 - Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (AM), Italy ([link](#))
 - University of Toronto (AM), Canada ([link](#))
- **Graphene Flagship Annual Meetings:**
 - In October 2024, GRAPHERGIA partners from FORTH, ADA, and AUS attended the Graphene Flagship Annual Meeting 2024, which took place as a satellite event at Graphene Week 2024.
 - In September 2025, FORTH represented GRAPHERGIA at the Graphene Flagship Annual Meeting 2025, which took place as a satellite event at Graphene Week 2025.
- **Graphene Flagship’s Science and Technology Forum 2024.** FORTH represented GRAPHERGIA in this event.
- **Graphene Flagship’s Science and Technology Forum 2025.** FORTH represented GRAPHERGIA in this event, participating in the topical workshops.

2.2.2 Graphene Week Participations

Graphene Week is the annual event dedicated to graphene-related research and organised by GF. Since its start, GRAPHERGIA has actively participated in two Graphene Week editions, which offer a great opportunity to present the project’s research progress through workshops and posters and to engage directly with ecosystem members and beyond. The following table provides a clear overview of GRAPHERGIA’s actions in these events, along with a link to more information in a dedicated blog post.

Table 3: Overview of GRAPHERGIA's participations in Graphene Weeks

Edition	Participating GRAPHERGIA partners	Key actions	Read more
Graphene Week 2025 (Vicenza, Italy)	FORTH, PLE, ADA, NTT, AUS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Workshop organization. ○ Presentation in a workshop on the LCA. ○ Two posters. ○ Podcast recording. 	https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/02/graphergia-at-graphene-week-2025-a-chronicle-of-energy-innovation-sustainability-and-connections

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Collaboration with sister projects: SAFARI, GIANCE, 2D-Biopad, MUNASET & ARMS. 	
Graphene Week 2024 (Prague, Republic Czech)	FORTH, ADA, NTT, UGE,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Workshop organization. ○ Two posters. ○ Collaboration with sister projects: ARMS 	https://graphergia.eu/2024/10/31/graphergia-at-the-graphene-week-2024-a-strong-grapheneeu-projects-community-is-key-for-our-common-good/

2.3 Established collaborations with sister projects

GRAPHERGIA has initiated or participated in 13 joint activities with **nine Graphene Flagship projects**, and beyond. These include webinar offerings, organising joint workshops, publishing articles, conducting technical collaborations, or even podcast recordings. The table below provides an insight into the established collaborations, while Annex 1 provides the full picture of these collaborations carried out regularly at the beginning of the project. Moreover, all collaborations have been documented with dedicated blog articles on the GRAPHERGIA website, under [activities-page](#).

Figure 3: FORTH represents GRAPHERGIA at the 9th EU-Korea Workshop hosted by 2D-Printable (May 2025)

Table 4: Summary of the collaborations with sister projects

Initiative	Topic	Implemented activity (timing)	Link
ARMS	Energy storage and harvesting	Three joint workshops (i) IEEE FLEPS in June 2024 (Finland) ii) SSC 2024, September 2024 (Czech Republic), iii) Graphene week 2024), technical/scientific collaboration and a podcast episode (continuous)	www.arms-project.eu
2D-Biopad	Graphene-enabled biosensing	Joint online article (April 2025)	https://2d-biopad.eu
MUNASET	Graphene-enabled biosensing	A joint podcast episode (continuous)	https://graphene-flagship.eu/focus/biomedical/munaset/

GIANCE	Life Cycle Assessment	Workshop speaker at Graphene week 2025 (September 2025)	www.giance-project.eu
SAFARI	Safe and sustainable 2D materials	Joint workshop at Graphene week 2025 (September 2025)	www.safari-project.eu
2D -Printable	Printed electronics	9 th EU Korea Workshop participation (May 2025) and technical collaboration; sample exchange (continuous)	https://2d-printable.eu
EMPHASIS	Energy storage	Joint workshop (September 2024)	www.emphasis-supercaps.eu
INERRANT	Next-generation and sustainable batteries	Joint workshop (September 2024)	https://www.inerrant-batteries.eu/
Battery 2030	Next-generation and sustainable batteries	Stakeholder engagement (continuous)	https://battery2030.eu/

2.4 Impact of the collaborations in Period 1

To recap, the collaboration activities carried out within the GRAPHERGIA Hub and the GF i ecosystem have positively impacted the GRAPHERGIA project in several key areas.

Table 5: Collaborations' impact in brief

Area	Impact
Knowledge sharing and synergy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synergies established within the GRAPHERGIA Hub (the project's own platform) and with 12 sister projects from GF i. • Accelerated learning via joint/ open webinars. • Interdisciplinary enrichment via joint publications and workshops. • Technical collaboration enables the exchange of samples and the comparison of scientific approaches.
Faster road from research to markets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More efficient and better knowledge transfer that are translated to products, technologies or processes. Stakeholder involvement and feedback are crucial for this.
Resource efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less redundancy: joint working groups / committees (standardisation, dissemination, LCA) enable to avoid working in same topics but in different silos. • Funding optimisation: leveraging ongoing similar efforts to carry out joint work (publications, communication efforts) or splitting occurring costs.
Stronger public awareness and visibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stronger networks attracting more stakeholders to the GRAPHERGIA activities and results. • Joint communication efforts highlight societal impact more effectively; especially, the GRAPHERGIA podcast as an example.
Capacity building and training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skill exchange: Researchers gain exposure to innovation practices (e.g., commercialization, prototyping), while innovators (especially SME / industrial partners) benefit from scientific rigor. • Training opportunities: Joint workshops foster the next generation of researchers and interdisciplinary experts.

Pending for EC approval

3 COMMUNICATION

The continuous communication activities focus on raising awareness among the target stakeholders. GRAPHERGIA’s communication content, channels and tools are continuously evolving based on the project’s progress, which contributes to the good visibility and public outreach, as the communication KPI’s status indicates. Since the submission of D7.1 (M6), this project phase run **early bird communication (Phase 2)** with focus on:

- Starting early communication based on the editorial plan.
- Engagement through owned communication channels and external media outlets.
- Development of communication materials based on the project’s evolution.
- Participation in varied stakeholder meetings and events.

3.1 Status of the Communication KPIs

Table 6: Status of the Communication KPIs

		GA Objective	Status in M25
Project Website	Total number of visits (by the end of the project)	60,000	15,463
Open virtual hub	No. of members	100	75
Zenodo	Downloads per public deliverable	250	426 (in total)
Newsletter	No. of published / featured newsletters	13	31
	No. of subscribers	600	594
Promotional material	e-material sent to No. of recipients	1,000	0
	No. of shared hard copy material	600	300
Videos & Podcasts	No. of views in Youtube	10,000	685
	No. of produced videos	10	6
	No. of unique listeners	1,000	0
	No. of produced podcast episodes	5	0
Social Media	No. of followers per social media account	1,500	2,084 (in total)
	No. of impressions (monthly average)		
Project workshops	No. of participants in 3 thematic workshops	200	422
Visits to schools	Visit at least 1 school per partner in its territory, No. of visits in total	12	13

3.2 Communication campaigns’ key content

Based on the communication strategy (part of D7.1), the communication activities have been carried out across the project’s established communication channels. The next chapter provides more insight into the key results.

The aim of the **GRAPHERGIA's communication plan is to generate awareness** about the project activities and their **impact at the scientific, social, economic, and environmental levels**. We put the focus on our **partners and their research**, making visible the importance of their innovations and **the human side of graphene**.

We can divide our content into three big content blocks that we will explain and analyze in the following pages of this report: **GRAPHERGIA brand awareness, GRAPHERGIA events and GRAPHERGIA in the international graphene and 2D materials community**, including the Graphene Flagship.

As it will be explained in the sections below (3.3. *Key results in communication* and 4.2.2. *Awareness publications*), **the best performing content is that related to events**, especially our participation in the **Graphene Week**, and the webinars organised by the **GRAPHERGIA Hub**, as well as the **interviews to present the partners**.

3.3 Key results in communication

3.3.1 Website

GRAPHERGIA's website (graphergia.eu) is the main project gateway. Operational since December 2023 (M3), it showcases the project's vision and methodology, research activities and outcomes, demo cases, team, community, news and events. Firstly, this section offers a look at the qualitative analysis of the website and secondly, at its quantitative performance as an efficient communication tool.

Figure 4: GRAPHERGIA website at a sight

Figure 5: The landing page banner

Besides the home, containing information about GRAPHERGIA’s smart e-textiles and Li-ion batteries, innovations, challenges, demo cases, methodology, and partners, the website has been structured into six pages:

1. About

The About page is a section containing detailed information about the GRAPHERGIA project, organised into four subpages:

- **The Project:** It explains the GRAPHERGIA project in detail, focusing on our needs, innovations, and impacts at the scientific, economic, and social levels.
 - **Objectives:** To successfully accomplish the ambitious milestones set by GRAPHERGIA, this page offers an overview of the eight project objectives.
 - **Methodology:** This section explains the project's approach to eco-friendly, sustainable methodologies and outlines the project's challenges.
 - **Lexicon:** It includes some technical terms and concepts used by the GRAPHERGIA innovators.
2. **Consortium:** It comprises 11 research and industrial partners from 6 European countries, coordinated by the Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas (FORTH)
 3. **Demo Cases:** It showcases the three demo cases of GRAPHERGIA.
 4. **Activities:** This page gets monthly updates, acting as the blog or news section of the GRAPHERGIA website. The articles uploaded are divided into seven categories, explained in depth in section 4.2.2. *Awareness publications* of this document.

Figure 6: A snapshot of the Activities-page

5. **Community:** The Community page is a section created with a dual use. The first is to explain why GRAPHERGIA belongs to the Graphene Flagship community, and the second is to provide a repository of the project's research outcomes. That is why it has been organised in four subpages:
 - **About the Community:** This page values our belonging to the Graphene Flagship community and showcases our sibling projects advancing technologies that rely on graphene and other 2-dimension (2D) materials.

- **Hub** (launched in January 2025): This section acts as the welcome page to the GRAPHERGIA Hub, where we connect stakeholders across European, national, and local landscapes driving innovation in graphene-enabled energy solutions, novel smart textiles or advancing future battery technologies.
- **Webinars** (launched in June 2025): After launching the GRAPHERGIA Hub in January 2025, we saw the need to create a webinars repository on our website. We have published two of them, the first one IPR management and the second, on sustainability and eco-design.

Figure 7: A snapshot of the Webinars-page

- **Resources** (launched in June 2025): This page also serves as a repository for the GRAPHERGIA project publications, including deliverables, communication and marketing materials, posters, and scientific publications.
6. **Contact**: This page is a contact form for visitors to send us emails for more information about GRAPHERGIA.

To continue, we propose further quantitative analysis of the website's efficiency as a communication tool.

WEBSITE VIEWS: Regarding the impact of the project website, after launching it at the end of December 2023 (M3), it has gathered a total of 15.000 page views accumulated from its launch until the 31st of October 2025 (M25). The total number of page views (over 23 months) averages 652 per month.

Figure 8: Website traffic M3-M25

WEBSITE USERS: A total of 1.700 users have visited the GRAPHERGIA website during the reporting period (M3-M25). They usually spend 3m 24s reading our website. The top five pages they visit the most are the following:

Table 7: Page views by the Content Category

Website page	Page views	Link
Home	3.590	https://graphergia.eu/
Activities	1.999	https://graphergia.eu/activities/
Consortium	675	https://graphergia.eu/consortium/
The Project	460	https://graphergia.eu/about/
Lexicon	412	https://graphergia.eu/about/lexicon/

The visitors that arrive at the GRAPHERGIA website come from organic social (30.88%), followed by direct (29.26%), organic search (20.45%) and referral (17.57%). As shown in the figures below, most of our users come from the United States (29.52%), Greece (10.61%), Italy (9.39%), Germany (6.67%), and Spain (6.12%). Smaller percentages come from France (5.64%), India (4.18%), Sweden (2.61%), the United Kingdom (1.88%) and the Netherlands (1.58%).

Figure 9: Geographical representation of the website visitors

3.3.2 Social media

GRAPHERGIA social media is the cornerstone of the project's daily communication and dissemination. **Active on LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), and BlueSky, we have a social media community of 2,084 followers.** Most of them are on LinkedIn (1,590), and a smaller part are on X (377) and BlueSky (117). All our posts on LinkedIn and X accumulate a total of 291,443 impressions, which, divided by 24 months (we launched our LinkedIn and X in November 2023 - M2), make **an average of 12,143 monthly impressions.** Most of the impressions come from LinkedIn (255,155) and a small part of them, from X (39,888).

In January 2025 (M16), we decided to open a third social media profile on BlueSky to reach a wider audience.

Table 8: GRAPHERGIA's social media

LinkedIn	X	BlueSky
@GRAPHERGIA	@graphergia.eu	@graphergia.bsky.social
1,590 followers	377 followers	117 followers
255,155 impressions	39,888 impressions	N/A

Figure 10: GRAPHERGIA's social media Headers

On these three channels, **the project publishes updates an average of three times per week**, adapting the content to each platform. This content is essentially related to the project and our activities (e.g., sharing our news, articles, and newsletters; promoting our participation in events and our post-event chronicles), as well as publishing our interviews to present to partners. In addition, it showcases the project methodology, research outcomes and objectives, the Graphene Flagship community and our sibling projects, and the graphene and 2D materials ecosystem.

In consequence, the featured content is organised into several social media campaigns:

- **GRAPHERGIA brand awareness:**
 - Website
 - Newsletter
 - Lexicon
 - Methodology
 - Impacts
 - Demo Cases
 - GRAPHERGIA Hub
- **GRAPHERGIA consortium:**
 - *Unveiling the Team behind the GRAPHERGIA Project - Meet our Partners*
 - *Inside the GRAPHERGIA Lab: Interviews with our Early-Career Researchers*
- **GRAPHERGIA events** (pre-event, during-event, and post-event)
 - Graphene Week 2024
 - Graphene Week 2025
 - GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinar Series
 - Other events
- **GRAPHERGIA research dissemination:**
 - Scientific publications
 - Scientific posters
 - Deliverables
- **GRAPHERGIA Press Releases, news and articles**
- **Graphene Flagship Community**
- **Graphene and 2D materials ecosystem**

The best-performing GRAPHERGIA social media campaigns include notably posts presenting the involvement of the researchers and partners in key stakeholder events.

Figure 11: Interview campaigns on social media¹

¹ Example: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7389637632462458881>

Figure 12: Example of an event-post on social media²

When analysing the stakeholder profiles reached on social media, it can be observed that the followers of the LinkedIn page come mainly from **Greece, Spain, India, Sweden, and the United Kingdom**. Regarding their job function, the top five is: **research (19%), business development (10.4%), education (9.9%), engineering (7.4%), and operations (6.4%)**. The rest come from other types of work related to project management, sales, marketing and communication.

By industry, most work in higher education, research services, nanotechnology research, IT services and consulting, and chemical manufacturing, which shows that the right targets are following the page, since GRAPHERGIA is a research project powering future energy with graphene (see Figure 13).

These followers interact with our content, since the GRAPHERGIA LinkedIn page has a **monthly average engagement rate of 11.2% during the past year (November 2024 - October 2025)**

² <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7379504042785452032>

Follower demographics

Figure 13: LinkedIn Follower Demographics M1-M25

3.3.3 Newsletters

GRAPHERGIA’s newsletters are published every six months. They are released via LinkedIn and the GRAPHERGIA website Newsletter section on the Activities page, and they are also shared on X and BlueSky. **The project has published four newsletters and accumulated 594 subscribers on LinkedIn.**

Table 9: GRAPHERGIA's Newsletters

Date	Title	Access
29/10/2025	GRAPHERGIA Newsflash #4 - October 2025: Advancing Sustainable Energy Solutions Across Europe	LinkedIn article Website article
03/04/2025	GRAPHERGIA Newsflash #3 - April 2025: Sustainability Assessment & Eco-Design for Graphene-Based Products	LinkedIn article Website article
07/11/2024	GRAPHERGIA Newsflash #2 - November 2024: Towards an Innovative Energy Landscape with Graphene for a Climate-Neutral Future	LinkedIn article Website article
26/03/2024	GRAPHERGIA Newsflash #1 - March 2024: Revolutionizing Energy Harvesting in Textiles and Battery Technology	LinkedIn article Website article

Figure 14: Example of the latest newsletter banner

In addition, GRAPHERGIA has been featured in **30 external newsletters** (see Annex 2 – List of the Featured External Newsletters). This enables us to leverage the well-established newsletters to reach more readers. For example, the AUSTRALO newsletter, which regularly features the project, has 734 subscribers.

Figure 15: From Graphene Flagship Quarterly Newsletter - February 2025_1

3.3.4 Press Release and External Online Media Platforms

The **first [press release](#)**, published in November 2023, enabled the project to gain visibility in external online media from the very start. To date, GRAPHERGIA has been featured in 28 online

media articles published by external platforms. Moreover, new press releases are issued when a major project milestone is announced, such as the start of the demonstrators foreseen for Q1 2027.

Table 10: External articles about the project

Date	Title	Publisher	Country	Website
30/10/2025	Laser-Induced Graphene and MXenes on Cross-Linked Polymer Substrates for Wearable Device	GFi	EU	https://graphene-flagship.eu/events/graphergia-hub-webinar-series-laser-induced-graphene-and-mxenes-on-cross-linked-polymer-substrates-for-wearable-devices/
27/08/2025	The GRAPHERGIA Project is "Back to School" at Graphene Week 2025	GFi	EU	https://graphene-flagship.eu/materials/news/the-graphergia-project-is-back-to-school-at-graphene-week-2025/
26/08/2025	Life Cycle Assessment Workshop	GFi	EU	https://graphene-flagship.eu/events-1/gw2025-chairs-committee/workshops-trainings/life-cycle-assessment-workshop/
26/08/2025	Safe and Sustainable-by-Design 2D Materials: Manufacturing Processes and Applications in Energy, Electronics, and Biotechnology	GFi	EU	https://graphene-flagship.eu/events-1/gw2025-chairs-committee/workshops-trainings/ssbd-2d-materials-workshop/
26/05/2025	9 th EU-Korea Workshop on	2D-Printable	EU	https://2d-printable.eu/9th-eu-koreaws-e-mrs-spring/
12/02/2025	Graphene energy storage for a sustainable future	Innovation News Network	EU	https://www.innovationnewsnetwork.com/graphene-energy-storage-for-a-sustainable-future/55442/
15/01/2025	Liaison Collaborations - GRAPHERGIA	GIANCE	EU	https://www.giance-project.eu/liaison-collaborations/
01/12/2024	Graphene Flagship Community	2D-PRINTABLE	EU	https://2d-printable.eu/graphene-flagship/
23/10/2024	Next-2Digits at Graphene Week 2024	Next2Digits	EU	https://next-2digits.eu/next-2digits-at-graphene-week-2024/
03/10/2024	ARMS unlocking innovation at GRAPHENE WEEK 2024 – Europe's leading conference on graphene and 2D materials	ARMS Project	EU	https://www.arms-project.eu/news_events/params/post/4659638/arms-unlocking-innovation-at-graphene-week-2024-europes-leading-conference-
20/08/2024	Bina-converting Smart Fabricanginit sa kuryente	Securities.io	Philippines	https://www.securities.io/tl/ang-matalinong-tela-ay-nagpapalit-ng-init-sa-kuryente/

04/07/2024	IEEE Fleps 2024 Gallery	SOLiD Project	EU	https://thesolidproject.eu/1216-2/
03/06/2024	6th IEEE International Conference on Flexible and Printable Sensors and Systems, FLEPS 2024	University of Tampere	Finland	https://researchportal.tuni.fi/en/activities/6th-ieee-international-conference-on-flexible-and-printable-senso
08/02/2024	Graphene Flagship common Kick-Off meeting and Science and Technology Forum (STF)	AMIRES	EU	https://www.amires.eu/graphene-flagship-common-kick-off-meeting-and-science-and-technology-forum-stf/
14/12/2023	GRAPHERGIA Project Launches for Energy Harvesting and Storing	Printed Electronics Now	US	https://www.printedelectronicsnow.com/contents/view_breaking-news/2023-12-14/graphergia-project-launches-for-energy-harvesting-and-storing/
13/12/2023	European innovators launch GRAPHERGIA project to revolutionise energy harvesting in textiles and battery technology	OPE Journal	Germany	https://opejournal.com/news/european-innovators-launch-graphergia-project-to-revolutionise-energy-harvesting-in-textiles-and-battery-technology
11/12/2023	Consortium to develop graphene-based materials	WTIN	UK	https://www.wtin.com/article/2023/december/11-12-23/consortium-to-develop-graphene-based-materials/
15/11/2023	European Innovators Launch GRAPHERGIA Project	Printed Electronics Now	US	https://www.printedelectronicsnow.com/contents/view_breaking-news/2023-11-15/european-innovators-launch-graphergia-project/
15/11/2023	European Innovators Launch GRAPHERGIA Project to Revolutionize Energy Harvesting in Textiles and Battery Technology	Nanotechnology Info & Statistics	Global	https://statnano.com/news/73126/European-Innovators-Launch-GRAPHERGIA-Project-to-Revolutionize-Energy-Harvesting-in-Textiles-and-Battery-Technology#ixzz8J7d3KdZx
13/11/2023	European Innovators Launch GRAPHERGIA Project to Revolutionize Energy Harvesting in Textiles and Battery Technology	ITS For Home	EU	https://www.itsforhome.com/2023/11/08/european-innovators-launch-graphergia-project-to-revolutionize-energy-harvesting-in-textiles-and-battery-technology/
13/11/2023	New project called GRAPHERGIA to revolutionize energy harvesting in textiles and battery technology	Polyester Time	EU	https://www.polyestertime.com/packaging-waste/
11/11/2023	GRAPHERGIA Project Launches to Revolutionize Energy Integration	ProlificNews	EU, North America & Asia	https://prolificnews.com/graphergia-project-launches-to-revolutionize-energy-integration/
11/11/2023	New project called GRAPHERGIA to revolutionize	Graphene-Info	EU	https://www.graphene-info.com/new-project-called-graphergia-

	energy harvesting in textiles and battery technology			revolutionize-energy-harvesting-textiles-and
10/11/2023	European Innovators Launch GRAPHERGIA Project to Revolutionize Energy Harvesting in Textiles and Battery Technology	Artic Portal	Iceland	https://arcticportal.org/ap-library/announcements/3370-european-innovators-launch-graphergia-project-to-revolutionize-energy-harvesting-in-textiles-and-battery-technology
10/11/2023	GRAPHERGIA Project To Revolutionize Energy Integration With €4.5M Funding	Technology Times	Pakistan	https://technologytimes.pk/2023/11/10/graphergia-project-to-revolutionize-energy-integration-with-e4-5m-funding/
10/11/2023	GRAPHERGIA project: Energy harvesting in textiles & battery tech	British Utilities	UK	https://british-utilities.co.uk/2023/graphergia-project-energy-harvesting-in-textiles-battery-tech/
9/11/2023	Graphene's Promise Becomes Concrete	The Innovator	France	https://theinnovator.news/graphenes-promise-becomes-concrete/
09/11/2023	European Innovators Launch GRAPHERGIA Project to Revolutionize Energy Harvesting in Textiles and Battery Technology	Graphene Flagship	EU	https://graphene-flagship.eu/materials/news/european-innovators-launch-graphergia-project-to-revolutionize-energy-harvesting-in-textiles-and-battery-technology/

3.3.5 Multimedia – videos and podcast series

Videos

To propose engaging content, GRAPHERGIA creates short videos that are shared across the project channels. The project's YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@graphergia>) has 23 subscribers and has shared eight videos, which have received 690+ views, as showcased in the table below.

Table 11: GRAPHERGIA's videos in open access

Date	Title	Views	Link
October 2024	GRAPHERGIA - Powering Future Energy with Graphene	211	www.youtube.com/watch?v=xL_3CNDdLLY
February 2025	GRAPHERGIA Joins the EU Graphene & 2D Materials Community in the Graphene Week 2024	48	www.youtube.com/watch?v=0fbr-k8498w
February 2025	GRAPHERGIA Project Interview with Despoina Batsouli - Adamant Composites	103	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8arkvhhWPHA
March 2025	GRAPHERGIA Project Interview with Elena Merli - Next Technology Tecnotessile	116	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q4omVrVWE58
April 2025	GRAPHERGIA Project Interview with Spyros Yannopoulos -	84	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BP01ffzzJ2Q

	Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas		
May 2025	GRAPHERGIA Project Interview with Philippe Basset - Université Gustave Eiffel	45	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KCkaG2_R9N8
April 2025	GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinar Series 2 - Sustainability Assessment & Eco-Design for Graphene-Based Products	40	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0pJJghVOk1k
September 2025	GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinar Series #1 - IPR Management with Kostas Vavekis	10	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=up1I7mNHTew
November 2025	GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinar Series 3 - Laser-Induced Graphene & MXenes on Polymers for Wearable Devices	10	www.youtube.com/watch?v=pKaGZbBDeoM

A podcast series

A second element used to propose more engaging content is the podcast series “**The Human Side of Graphene**”: the first two episodes were recorded in collaboration with sister projects, including Graphene Flagship, ARMS, MUNASET, 2D-BioPAD at Graphene Week 2025. Four more episodes will be created. The aim is to disseminate the impact and benefits of the Graphene Flagship project’s research on graphene and 2D materials for our society. **This podcast series will be released in January 2026** and published across GRAPHERGIA's communication channels and on a dedicated podcast platform.

These two episodes are:

- **Episode #1 - "Charging the Future: How Graphene Fuels Sustainability"** hosted by Maria Abrahamsson (Graphene Flagship's Director).
- **Episode #2 - "Smart Materials, Smarter Medicine: Graphene Biosensors in Healthcare"** hosted by Amaia Zurutuza (Graphenea).

3.3.6 Promo material

The project uses dedicated **promo materials to engage external stakeholders**, including the project’s [one-pager](#) and a [roll-up banner](#). Partners use the roll-up banner across different events, and especially at the Graphene Week project exhibition area. The flyers are shared both virtually (as part of stakeholder engagement emails) and in print (for now, 300 printed copies have been distributed).

Figure 16: Mock-ups of GRAPHERGIA Promo Material

As described in the previous version of this deliverable (D7.1), GRAPHERGIA has a dedicated branding strategy that helps identify the project and its mission. In line with this, based on the consortium needs, AUSTRALO continuously creates multiple graphical materials (e.g., visual banners, infographics, poster templates) to support the project's communication and dissemination activities.

Figure 17: Examples of GRAPHERGIA visuals in action

4 DISSEMINATION

The continuous dissemination activities enable target stakeholders to use the project results, including scientific publications, webinars, workshops, and public deliverables. Dissemination activities complement communication and run throughout the project (from M1 to M42).

4.1 Status of the Dissemination KPIs

The key performance indicators are progressing smoothly in line with the plan outlined in Deliverable 7.1. The consortium has published **10 scientific papers** in journals or at conferences held in Europe and beyond (the US, Canada, South Korea, and Japan). The partners have attended **16 external stakeholder events** to present GRAPEHRGIA's research. And **12 early-career researchers** are working on the project.

The only two KPI pending for the moment are the Best Practice handbook, due at the end of the project, and the diffusion of the results to association members, which is related to the publication of the handbook. For both pending KPIs, an action plan is provided in section 4.2.2. The table below shows the status of the dissemination KPIs as of M25 (October 31st, 2025).

Table 12: Status of the Dissemination KPIs

		GA Objective	Status in M25
Publications	Peer-reviewed articles in scientific research publications in international journals or conferences	15	10
Official EU tools	Use of key tools	4	1
	Articles published in EU magazines	5	2
GRAPHERGIA Best Practice handbook	Views / downloads	1,000	0
Diffusion of the project results to associations' members	Number of reached Organisations (<i>Smart-X, Smart textile alliance, Smarttex network, Battery 2030+ initiative, European Battery Alliance</i>)	100	0
Research educational activities	MSc related to GRAPHERGIA research	5	2
	PhD theses related to GRAPHERGIA research	5	10
	Students reached	300	626
Clustering and networking activities with stakeholders,	Created joint actions	3	13
Events	No. of events in total	30	19
	No. of scientific events participated		16
	No. of non-scientific events participated		3

4.2 Key results in dissemination

This section describes the key results of GRAPHERGIA's dissemination activities, which are tightly related to activities detailed also under the previous section (e.g., community building and communication).

4.2.1 Scientific publications

GRAPHERGIA has already published 10 peer-reviewed scientific papers in open access: 5 in scientific journals and 5 in conference proceedings (see Table 13). All scientific publications are shared on GRAPHERGIA's website, on the [resources-page](#), as well as on the project's [Zenodo library](#).

Table 13: GRAPHERGIA's Scientific Publications

Publication type	Title	Publication venue	Issue / Date	Link
Publication in conference proceedings	Ionic liquid integrated high-voltage polymer gel electrolyte to improve the capacitance and cyclic stability of supercapacitors	mESC-IS 2025	4 September 2025	https://zenodo.org/records/17105894
Publication in conference proceedings	Polymer Electrolyte Based Flexible Micro-Supercapacitors for Future Aerospace and Smart e-Textile Applications	the 247th ECS Meeting (The Electrochemical Society)	18-22 May 2025	https://zenodo.org/records/15576112
Publication in conference proceedings	Fabrication of Laser-induced Micro-Supercapacitors for structurally-integrated power storage systems	the 50th International Conference on Micro-and Nano Engineering (MNE2024)	16-19 September 2024	https://graphergia.eu/2025/05/15/graphergia-abstract-fabrication-of-laser-induced-micro-supercapacitors-for-structurally-integrated-power-storage-systems/
Publication in conference proceedings	Quasi-solid polymer electrolytes for all-in-one self-charging structural energy storage devices	Conference on Solid State Chemistry 2024 (SSC 2024)	ISBN 978-80-7414-866-8	https://graphergia.eu/2025/05/15/graphergia-abstract-quasi-solid-polymer-electrolytes-for-all-in-one-self-charging-structural-energy-storage-devices/
Article in Journal	Temperature Dependence of Coherent versus Spontaneous Raman Scattering	Physical Review Letters	Phys. Rev. Lett. 133, 206902 – Published 15 November, 2024	https://graphergia.eu/2025/05/15/graphergia-scientific-publication-temperature-dependence-of-coherent-versus-

				spontaneous-raman-scattering/
Article in Journal	Solving ZIB challenges: the dynamic role of water in deep eutectic solvents electrolyte	Journal of Materials Chemistry A	2025,13, 9778-9790	https://graphergia.eu/2025/05/15/graphergia-scientific-publication-solving-zib-challenges-the-dynamic-role-of-water-in-deep-eutectic-solvents-electrolyte/
Article in Journal	X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy analysis of electrospun polyacrylonitrile fibres: Pre- and post-thermal stabilisation investigations	Surface Science Spectra, Special Collection: Materials for Energy and the Environment	Volume 31, Issue 2 December 2024	https://graphergia.eu/2025/03/07/graphergia-scientific-publication-x-ray-photoelectron-spectroscopy-analysis-of-electrospun-polyacrylonitrile-fibers/
Article in Journal	Power management technologies for triboelectric nanogenerators	MRS BULLETIN	VOLUME 50 • MARCH 2025.	https://graphergia.eu/2025/03/03/graphergia-scientific-publication-power-management-technologies-for-triboelectric-nanogenerators/
Article in Journal	Dry laser-assisted fabrication of F-doped graphene electrodes: Boosting performance of Zn-ion hybrid capacitors	Chemical Engineering Journal	Volume 507, 1 March 2025, 160505	https://graphergia.eu/2025/02/14/graphergia-scientific-publication-dry-laser-assisted-fabrication-of-f-doped-graphene-electrodes-boosting-the-performance-of-zn-ion-hybrid-capacitors/
Publication in Conference proceedings	On the optimal choice of electrical conditioning circuits for triboelectric nanogenerators	PowerMEMS+ 2024: Micro and Miniature Power Systems, Self-Powered Sensors and Energy Autonomous Devices	18-21 November 2024	https://graphergia.eu/2025/01/28/scientific-publication-on-the-optimal-choice-of-electrical-conditioning-circuits-for-triboelectric-nanogenerators/

In addition, the project counts **four posters** presented during the poster sessions during Graphene Week (in 2024 and in 2025).

Table 14: GRAPHERGIA Posters from Graphene Week

Poster title	Event	Link
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In-situ laser reduction of graphene oxide on textiles: from lab-scale optimization to roll-to-roll manufacturing	Graphene Week 2025	https://zenodo.org/records/17350285
Reduced Graphene Oxide & CFRP's Maximized Properties: An Investigative Overview	Graphene Week 2025	https://zenodo.org/records/17350189
Innovative pilot lines for sustainable Graphene-based flexible and structural energy harvesting and storage devices	Graphene Week 2024	https://zenodo.org/records/14180043
Smart textiles based on triboelectric nanogenerators	Graphene Week 2024	https://zenodo.org/records/14180493

4.2.2 Awareness publications

One section of the GRAPHERGIA website, Activities, features monthly blog posts highlighting the project's achievements and progress. These blog posts are classified into seven key content categories, including:

- Articles and news
- Deliverables
- Events
- Interviews
- Newsletters
- Press Releases
- Scientific Publications

From the beginning of the project until October 2025, **70 blog posts have been published** (see Annex 3 – List of all GRAPHERGIA blog posts). Of these, **most of the content on the Activities page belongs to the Events category** (24), followed by Articles and News (16), Scientific Publications (12), Interviews (10), Newsletters (4), Deliverables (3), and Press Releases (1).

This shows the commitment of the GRAPHERGIA partners to disseminate our preliminary research results at scientific and non-scientific international events, for which many of our innovators publish scientific papers (abstracts, papers, posters, presentations, etc.).

These posts also share the project's achievements and milestones (in the Articles and News category) and promote the collaborations and profiles of involved researchers and PhD/MSc students (in the Interviews category).

20th edition of Graphene Week, held in a rainy Vicenza (Italy) from 22 to 26 September 2025 under the auspices of the Graphene Flagship, provided a vibrant and fertile platform for GRAPHERGIA to share its vision, engage new collaborators, and strengthen ties within the graphene community. Over five days of talks, workshops, posters, networking, and podcasts, the GRAPHERGIA Innovators had multiple opportunities to present their ongoing research and deepen the project's footprint in the European graphene-energy landscape.

Figure 18: Example³ of a blog post on the Activity page

About the blog post content performance

When analysing the data provided by Annex 3, it can be observed that the best-performing content analysed during this reporting period is interviews. **With FORTH (Spyros Yannopoulos), Adamant Composites (Despoina Batsouli), DLR (Blige Saruhan) and Pleione Energy (Athanasios Masouras) being the four most popular, with 227, 132, 105 and 98 views, respectively. Content related to the Graphene Week is also relevant to readers, since the blog post announcing our activities at Graphene Week 2025 has accumulated 134 views, and the one for 2024, 117; meanwhile, the Graphene Week 2024 post-event chronicle has 121 views.**

Moreover, **the launch of the first GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinar Series on IPR** was also interesting for the website visitors, with 112 views, and **content related to how our project is organised ("How does the GRAPHERGIA Project Work?")**, also attracts them, with 111 views. The top 10 most visited GRAPHERGIA blog posts (highlighted in bold in the table above) are closed by **the press release of our kick-off meeting** in the Greek city of Patras, with 107 views.

This means that interviews and events, especially Graphene Week and the GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinar Series, are the most-read content on the Activities page. But branded content to generate awareness about our project also seems to awaken the curiosity of our readers.

Hence, this blog post's content performance on the GRAPHERGIA website matches the best-performing posts from our social media campaigns on LinkedIn, X, and BlueSky, which are also

³ <https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/02/graphergia-at-graphene-week-2025-a-chronicle-of-energy-innovation-sustainability-and-connections/>

related to the consortium partners and their involvement in the project, as well as to our event attendance to disseminate our research activities and preliminary results.

This observation will guide the project in creating content that attracts future viewers from the target stakeholder groups.

Other awareness publications

GRAPHERGIA has presented its ambition, progress, and initial research results in **two editions of the Graphene Flagship annual reports**, which are primarily targeted at European policymakers in charge of 2D and nanomaterials and their applications. These publications aim to present the impact of the EU funding on the graphene-enabled innovation.

- [The Graphene Flagship Initiative Annual Report 2023](#) was released in June 2024.
- [The Graphene Flagship Initiative Annual Report 2024](#) was released in June 2025.

Best practice handbook – plan

As described in Section 1.2, the best practice handbook is one of the WP7 deliverables with a KPI of 1000 views or downloads. This report is due in the final project month, and it aims to leave a legacy for the GRAPHERGIA Hub, showcasing how collaboration and a community of knowledge exchange can be a game-changer in sustaining the impact of innovation initiatives.

This report aims to trigger new collaborations and opportunities beyond the GRPHAPHERGIA project, and to raise public awareness of EU-supported activities, essentially in the fields of smart textiles, next-gen Li-Ion batteries and graphene-enabled innovation, which contribute to building a greener tomorrow. In line with another Dissemination KPI, this report will be shared through an engaging one-to-one mailing campaign to relevant EU stakeholders, organisations and associations (e.g., Smart-X, ETP, Smart Textile Alliance, Smarttex Network, Battery 2030+ Initiative, European Battery Alliance, IAM4EU, etc.).

4.2.3 Webinars & Workshops

Webinars are an efficient tool for dissemination, as they enable not only presenting the work to stakeholders but also directly exchanging with them. GRAPHERGIA has hosted **three in-house webinars gathering 110 participants**; these are further described in section 2.1.1 as part of the GRAPHERGIA Hub activities.

In addition, GRAPHERGIA has (co-)hosted **8 workshops** discussing the project's innovation topics and **gathering 420+ workshop participants** for the interactive sessions. These workshops have enabled the consortium to build connections with related initiatives and their researchers, establish synergies, and leverage dissemination efforts.

Figure 19: Workshop with the SAFARI Project (May 2025)

These events have been fruitful platforms for meeting fellow researchers and innovators (as demonstrated in Figure 19). Moreover, the table below provides more information about the contributed workshops.

Table 15: List of GRAPHERGIA's Workshop Contributions

Date	Workshop Title	Sister projects involved	Name of the related event	Link to the article
25/09/2025	“Safe and Sustainable-by-Design 2D Materials: Manufacturing Processes and Applications in Energy, Electronics, and Biotechnology”	GRAPHERGIA and SAFARI joint workshop	Workshop co-organised with SAFARI at the Graphene Week 2025 (Vicenza, Italy). Involving two partners, FORTH (Nadia Bali) and NTT (Matteo Maccanti) as speakers.	Link
24/09/2025	Life Cycle Assessment Workshop	GIANCE (organiser) and Fraunhofer ICT	Workshop co-organized by GIANCE and Fraunhofer ICT at the Graphene Week 2025 (Vicenza, Italy). NTT (Matteo Maccanti) participates as an invited speaker	Link
26/05/2025	EU-Korea Workshop 2025	Graphene Flagship, 2D-PRINTABLE, 2D-PL, 2D-NEURALVISION, ARMS, GIANCE	FORTH (Prof. Spyros Yannopoulos) speaker participation – hosted in Strasbourg, France.	Link

15/05/2025	Graphene Flagship Digital Workshop: Advancing Sustainability in 2D Materials	SIO GRAFEN, SAFARI, ARMS	Organized by Graphene Flagship: NTT (Matteo Maccanti) speaker participation (online).	Link
09/05/2025	Safe and sustainable by design: graphene and maxenes	SAFARI, 2D-BioPAD	Collaboration Workshop involving SAFARI, GRAPHERGIA and 2DBioPad. FORTH (Prof. Spyros Yannopoulos) spoke in this workshop hosted by SAFARI (in Athens, Greece).	Link
15/10/2024	Integrating Graphene Innovations: From Smart Textiles to High-Performance Energy Storage	GRAPHERGIA and ARMS joint workshop	Graphene Week 2024 (in Prague, Czech Republic) workshop sessions hosted by ARMS and GRAPHERGIA. FORTH (Prof. Spyros Yannopoulos), ADA (Despoina Batsouli) and UGE (Philippe Basset) were speakers.	Link
8-13/09/2024	Electrochemical Energy Storage Materials and Processes	EMPHASIS INERRANT	15th International Conference on Solid State Chemistry 2024 (SSC 2024) (in Ústí nad Labem, Czech Republic). FORTH (Prof. Spyros Yannopoulos) and DLR (Dr. Apurba Ray) presented their research.	Link
30/06/2024	Synergizing Sustainability: Integrating Advanced Energy Storage with Harvesting for Wearable Electronics	GRAPHERGIA and SAFARI joint workshop	International Conference on Flexible and Printable Sensors and Systems (IEEE Fleps) (in Tampere, Finland). FORTH (Prof. Spyros Yannopoulos) and PLE (Dorela Hoxha) give presentations.	Link

4.2.4 Third-party Event Participations

The entire project consortium has been actively presenting their work across **19 European and international events on innovation in 2D materials, e-textiles, and energy solutions** across different application areas, such as defence and renewable energies. The **16 scientific events**, listed in Table 9, offered opportunities to present the project's progress **in conference proceedings or keynote presentations** and to connect with academic fellows working on the relevant topics.

Table 16 Participated Scientific Events

Dates	Event	Lead partner	Location	More information
12/10/2025	The 248th ECS Meeting	FORTH	Chicago, United States	https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/28/graphergia-at-the-248th-ecs-meeting-exploring-graphenes-potential-in-electrochemical-energy-storage/
22-26/09/2025	Graphene Week 2025	FORTH	Vicenza, Italy	https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/02/graphergia-at-graphene-week-2025-a-chronicle-of-energy-

				innovation-sustainability-and-connections/
1-5/09/2025	ISE20	UGE	Matsue, Japan	https://graphergia.eu/2025/09/12/graphergia-at-ise20-exploring-the-future-of-textile-tribo-electrets-for-energy-harvesting/
1-4/09/2025	mESC-IS 2025: International Symposium on Materials for Energy Storage and Conversion	DLR	Izmir, Turkey	https://graphergia.eu/2025/09/10/graphergia-at-mesc%e2%80%91is-2025-pioneering-graphene-innovation-in-energy-storage-and-conversion/
18-22 May 2025	247th ECS Meeting (The Electrochemical Society)	DLR	Montréal, Canada	https://graphergia.eu/2025/06/09/graphergias-may-2025-event-calendar-spreading-our-research-all-over-the-world/
18-21/11/2024	PowerMEMS+ 2024: Micro and Miniature Power Systems, Self-Powered Sensors and Energy Autonomous Devices	UGE	Tonsberg, Norway	https://graphergia.eu/2024/12/03/graphergia-presents-its-first-scientific-paper-at-powermems-2024/
14-18/10/2024	Graphene Week 2024	FORTH	Prague, Czech Republic	https://graphergia.eu/2024/10/31/graphergia-at-the-graphene-week-2024-a-strong-grapheneeu-projects-community-is-key-for-our-common-good/
16-18/09/2024	Micro-Nano Engineering (MNE) 2024	DLR	Montpellier, France	https://graphergia.eu/2024/10/24/graphergia-joins-the-micro-and-nano-engineering-mne-2024-conference-with-a-presentation-about-supercapacitors-for-power-storage/
15-18/09/2024	XXXVIII Panhellenic Conference on Solid State Physics & Materials Science'	FORTH	Ioannina, Greece	https://graphergia.eu/2024/10/02/a-phd-student-from-forth-speaks-about-her-graphergia-research-at-the-xxxviii-panhellenic-conference-on-solid-state-physics-and-materials-science/
8-13/09/2024	15th International Conference on Solid State Chemistry (SSC 2024)	DLR	Ústí nad Labem, Czech Republic	https://graphergia.eu/2024/09/22/graphergia-co-hosts-the-horizon-europe-satellite-event-at-the-15th-international-conference-on-solid-state-chemistry-2024-with-the-emphasis-and-inerrant-projects/

19-23/08/2024	Materials Challenges in Alternative and Renewable Energy 2024 (MCARE'24)	UGE	Jeju (South Korea)	https://graphergia.eu/2024/09/29/our-partner-universite-gustave-eiffel-participates-in-the-materials-challenges-in-alternative-and-renewable-energy-2024-conference-with-a-symposium/
28/07-02/08/2024	28th International Conference on Raman Spectroscopy – ICORS 2024	URM	Rome, Italy	https://graphergia.eu/2024/09/26/the-graphergia-partner-sapienza-university-of-rome-hosts-the-28th-international-conference-on-raman-spectroscopy/
30/06 – 03/072024	International Conference on Flexible and Printable Sensors and Systems (IEEE FLEPS)	FORTH	Tampere, Finland	https://graphergia.eu/2024/07/30/graphergia-participates-in-a-workshop-about-synergizing-sustainability-in-the-ieee-fleps-2024-conference-in-tampere/
25/06/2024	ICOOMPA Conference - 10th International Conference on Optical, Optoelectronic and Photonic Materials and Applications	FORTH	Pardubice, Czech Republic	https://graphergia.eu/2024/07/01/graphergia-participates-at-the-icoompa-2024-conference-with-an-invited-talk-about-laser-sources-to-produce-high-quality-graphene/
27-31/5/2024	e-MRS 2024 Spring Meeting	UGE	Strasbourg, France	https://graphergia.eu/2024/06/25/a-graphergia-partner-co-hosts-a-symposium-on-nanogenerators-at-the-european-materials-research-society-2024-spring-meeting/

The partners have presented GRAPHERGIA's ambitions and innovations at three non-scientific events, as listed on Table 17. At the **DEFEA exhibition**, dedicated to international defence solutions, ADAMANT showcased the project's innovation, especially related to smart textiles and new-gen Li-ion batteries, which could be further applied in the defence sector. Whereas at **Large-area, Organic & Printed Electronics Convention (LOPEC) 2025**, Born showcased the GRAPHERGIA project to key industry players.

Figure 20: Adamant team at the DEFEA Event

Table 17: Non-scientific events

Dates	Event	Lead partner	Location	More information
6-8 May 2025	DEFEA exhibition	ADA	Athens, Greece	https://graphergia.eu/2025/06/09/graphergias-may-2025-event-calendar-spreading-our-research-all-over-the-world/
27/02/2025	LOPEC (Large-area, Organic & Printed Electronics Convention)	Born	Munich, Germany	https://graphergia.eu/2025/02/27/graphergia-presented-at-large-area-organic-printed-electronics-convention-lopec-2025/
5-6/ 02/2024	Graphene Flagship Joint Kick-off	FORTH	Gothenbourg, Sweden	https://graphergia.eu/2024/02/06/joint-kick-off-meeting-with-the-graphene-flagship-sister-projects-establishing-contacts-and-opportunities-for-synergies/

4.2.5 Engagement with the next generation of researchers, students and schools

The consortium’s academic partners work with next-generation researchers and students, presenting them with the opportunities offered by EU-funded research and innovation actions.

Next generation of researchers

12 Master-level students, PhD fellows and postdoctoral fellows have been involved, either full-time or part-time, in conducting GRAPHERGIA's research at UGE, DRM and FORTH. This is an opportunity for the fellows to work on their theses and prepare for their doctoral defences. To shed light on these profiles, the project has launched a communication campaign dedicated to the involved early-career researchers. This campaign was launched in October 2025, and a new interview is published every month.

Figure 21: First early-career interview⁴

Engagement with schools and students

As part of the “Open Doors for Schools” program, the Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences at FORTH (ICE-HT), the GRAPHERGIA project coordinator, annually invites local schools via the Secondary Education Authority of Western Greece to tour its facilities. Aimed at students aged 14–18 years old, the program introduces cutting-edge research in areas such as environmental science, advanced materials, renewable energy, and biotechnology/biomedicine, and introduces the students to modern scientific instrumentation.

In the 2024–2025 school year, 623 students from 13 schools (10 high schools and 3 middle schools) participated in the program in which GRAPHERGIA was presented. Vasilis Dracopoulos, a member of the FORTH team, was the responsible person for the reception of the students and the presentation of the main activities of the Institute, including GRAPHERGIA.

School visits are part of GRAPHERGIA's Dissemination and Communication strategy to reach and interact with stakeholders to promote our project and its results, in this case, students.

4.2.6 Usage of EU tools

The project has benefited from one official EU tool, namely the **Horizon Results Booster service**, which was consulted for the initial exploitation plans. HS Booster provided online training on August 1st, 2024, about the KER definition and proposed a set of tools to manage exploitation. It delivered its final report to GRAPHERGIA in November 2024; this service was used to understand

⁴ <https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/16/inside-the-graphergia-lab-interviews-with-our-early-career-researchers-sangha-mitra/>

alternative ways to manage the exploitation of results. The results are further described in deliverable 7.4.

In addition, towards the end of the project, as key exploitable results become increasingly tangible, the GRAPHERGIA beneficiaries will deploy the **Horizon Results Platform**⁵ to showcase their results.

Pending for EC approval

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

5 EXPLOITATION

Together with communication and dissemination, exploitation and Intellectual Property (IP) management are the crucial building blocks for sustaining the impact of the GRAPHERGIA project. The exploitation strategy was defined in Deliverable 7.1, and during this reporting it has been running as planned. Essentially, the consortium has continued to define further the target markets, the added value of the Key Exploitable Results (KER), the envisaged exploitation paths and the IP strategies.

5.1 Exploitation activities

During this reporting period, five internal workshops dedicated to exploitation have been hosted, and all consortium partners that are KER owners are actively involved in these sessions throughout the project.

- **An initial workshop:** During the project's kick-off meeting in Patras (Greece), the partners began strategic thinking about the planned project results. The idea was to encourage partners to start thinking about their exploitation models, and relevant customer groups and markets from the very early research phases. These discussions supported the exploitation plan drafting (D7.1).
- **Value proposition Workshop⁶:** On April 11th, 2024, AUS delivered a masterclass to the consortium on the exploitation steps planned throughout the project. The partners were invited to brainstorm the project results around the value proposition canvas.
- **Key Exploitable Results (KER) workshop** took place on January 10th, 2025, and it was an internal session to refine the key exploitable outcomes, their ownerships, result types and related demo cases. This session resulted in an internal database listing the key exploitable results and their definitions (description, IPR owner, added value, target markets, envisaged exploitation paths etc.).
- **The Market Analysis & Insights validation workshop⁷** took place on October 21st, 2025. The first part, AUS presented the analysis of GRAPHERGIA's target markets, GRAPHERGIA's added value and GRAPHERGIA's competitive advantage, focusing on our Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and their relation to our three demo cases.
- **The Business Challenges and Requirements workshop** took place in November 2025 with the aim of continuing discussions on IPR management across the beneficiaries for each of the eight Key Exploitable Results. This session also included an interactive part where the beneficiaries brainstormed the key challenges and requirements related to the KERs. The collected data will be used to further define the KERs' innovation management.

⁶ <https://graphergia.eu/2024/04/18/australo-hosts-the-first-graphergia-exploitation-workshop-for-the-graphergia-project-partners/>

⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7387439184044806144/>

In addition to these workshops, the partners have conducted desktop research, especially on market insights, and have exchanged with the industrial reference group, collecting their first feedback on the project's scientific and industrial added value.

Figure 22: Example of an internal exploitation workshop session

5.2 Key Exploitable Results and Innovation Management Strategies

5.2.1 KERs – the building blocks of GRAPHERGIA Market Analysis

Before describing the Key Exploitable Results, it is essential to remember the objectives and the context of GRAPHERGIA's ambition. The GRAPHERGIA project aims to unlock the potential of laser-assisted graphene production to shape the future of smart, self-charging textiles and next-generation Li-ion batteries. The resulting energy solutions innovations are implemented in real-life applications and revolutionary products, enabling essential advances required to successfully overcome current challenges in 2D materials for harvesting and storage applications.

In general terms, the three main objectives are to develop:

- **Self-powered e-Textiles:** GRAPHERGIA has initiated the creation of all-in-one, multifunctional self-charging power textiles, seamlessly integrating advanced electronic systems into the fabric. In addition to providing battery-free solutions for wearables, this technology offers a user-centric interface to the IoT through wireless transmission of sensor signals. This can serve users, especially in eHealth, sports and defence sectors, where body tracking is essential.
- **Next generation Li-Ion Batteries:** By leveraging the partners' tech know-how and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)-protected technologies, GRAPHERGIA is working on a dry-electrode fabrication approach for producing advanced graphene-based electrodes for next-generation Li-ion batteries. The project employs a comprehensive approach that integrates 2D materials and process-oriented methodologies, utilising cost-effective raw materials and scalable fabrication techniques to ensure economically viable and environmentally sustainable solutions.
- **Self-powered, structurally integrated sensor for aerospace:** GRAPHERGIA is pioneering the development of novel self-powered, structurally integrated graphene-based sensors designed for continuous, wireless monitoring of advanced composite materials. These embedded sensing systems will provide real-time information on the material state, enhancing safety, reliability, and operational efficiency in critical applications such as aerospace, automotive, and wind energy sectors.

Moreover, the resulting innovations are piloted in three use cases, including,

- All-in-one self-charging textile capable of energy harvesting and storage (demo case #1)
- Self-powered, structurally integrated sensor for aerospace structures (demo case #2)
- Advanced graphene-based LIB module prototype for space applications (demo case #3).

Targeted Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs)

The GRAPHERGIA innovation started at the research TRL level, level 3 or 4, depending on the component, and at the end of the project, it will achieve at least TRL 5; all technologies are validated in relevant environments.

GRAPHERGIA's Technology Readiness Levels

Figure 23: The Targeted TRL

Especially related to the validation leading the way towards further exploitation of the project results, the three GRAPHERGIA demo cases (run in WP5) are kicked off in M30 (March 2026), and all of these begin at TRL2-3, where the experimental proof of concept exists, and result in TRL5 validations in relevant environments.

GRAPHERGIA's laser-driven, eco-design approaches generate foundational advances in 2D-materials science, from novel precursors to record-performance devices. These results position GRAPHERGIA at the forefront of greener materials science, next-generation batteries and smart textiles.

Moreover, GRAPHERGIA's innovation will yield eight key exploitable results (KERs), which are either products, components, or processes, all part of the cutting-edge framework that deploys laser-assisted graphene-based materials directly into pertinent energy-harvesting and storage devices. These KERs are all piloted in at least one of the three GRAPHERGIA demo cases (described in the following sections).

Figure 24: GRAPHERGIA's Eight Key Exploitable Results

Table 18: GRAPHERGIA's Key Exploitable Results Definitions

KER Name & Type	Target market	IP-Background	Owners
<p>#1 Laser Roll-2-Roll Graphene on Textiles [Process]</p>	E-textile, Smart sensors	Graphene deposition on textiles by laser-based method. Application No.: 248-0004498129 (03/2022; FORTH and ADA)	FORTH, ADA
<p>#2 Graphene/Si Nanohybrid for Li-ion Batteries [Process]</p>	Li-ion Battery	A method for preparing graphene films using laser sources. Appl. No.: PCT/GR2021/000029 (05/2021; FORTH).	FORTH, PLE, ADA

<p>#3 Plasma-Enhanced Chemical Organic Coatings on Graphene [Process]</p>	E-textile, Smart sensors	<p>Background IP belongs to P2i and NTT for using PE-CVD to coat various surfaces as barriers.</p> <p>P2i open to granting us a license for the commercial exploitation of the method in this new application area.</p>	P2i Background IP; FORTH Foreground IP; NTT
<p>#4 FlexiGel-Micro-Super Capacitors 4 e-Textiles [Process]</p>	E-textile	N/A	DLR, FORTH, ADA
<p>#5 High-Voltage Plasma Switch 4 e-Textiles [Component / Process]</p>	E-textile	<p>Conditioning system for a triboelectric nanogenerator or an electrostatic kinetic energy harvester", EP 3 654 513 A1, Application no: 18020610.4, (15.11.2018, UGE)</p>	UGE, FORTH, ADA
<p>#6 KineticMesh Shelf-Charging IoT-enabled Power Textile [Product]</p>	E-textile	Based on the background IP of dependent KERs	Born GmbH, FORTH, ADA
<p>#7 Structurally Integrated Self-Powered AeroSensor [Product]</p>	Smart sensors	N/A	ADA, FORTH, UGE, DLR
	Li-ion Battery	<p>Previous patent in Pleione: Method for providing an electrode: European Patent Application No. 24386095.4, application number of EP24386095.4</p>	PLE, ADA, FORTH

#8 OrbitCell Graphene LIB 4 Space Apps [Product]			
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Pending for EC approval

5.2.1.1 The GRAPHERGIA innovations: Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD)

Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) form an important building block of the GRAPHERGIA innovation results that are considered in the exploitation models for the final products resulting from the project. All processes use water-based or solvent-free precursors, avoid PFAS and toxic binders for the LIB anodes, and concentrate energy input locally via lasers. The employed process minimizes waste, hazardous chemicals, and energy consumption.

In this sense SSbD framework combines LCA, LCC and eco-design analysis, and it is developed with **Work Package 6 "Life-cycle assessment, sustainability, and eco-design approach"** (lead by NTT). This framework suggests significantly lower energy use and increased cost savings per electrode compared to conventional wet-chemical routes.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Cost (LCC) analysis

GRAPHERGIA conducts an assessment that evaluates and quantifies both capital and operational costs, as well as potential cost savings, arising from the implementation of the proposed innovations across all stages—from material development to various supply chain configurations. The analysis employs the Life Cycle Costing (LCC) approach, which will be carried out in parallel with the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).

The LCC methodology follows a two-step process: Cost Identification – mapping and quantifying all relevant cost elements along the process chain; Cost-Benefit Analysis – evaluating the economic viability and efficiency of the proposed solutions.

Once the full process chain for manufacturing the novel materials and related devices/products developed within the GRAPHERGIA project is defined, specific cost models will be created. These models will estimate various costs based on key parameters within the process chain. In addition to cost estimation, the models will serve as tools for process optimisation, helping to identify potential bottlenecks and inefficiencies. Ultimately, the LCC analysis will support the selection of the most economically advantageous alternatives in terms of processes and products. The goal is to enable a comprehensive evaluation of cost reductions and guide strategic decisions based on the principle of delivering not just the “best value for money,” but the “best value over the entire asset life cycle”. The initial LCA and LCA assessments for GRAPHERGIA are described in deliverable 6.1, submitted in September 2025.

Eco-design

The eco-design research focuses on the recyclability and reusability of all resulting GRAPHERGIA components and deployed materials. This analysis, carried out in task 6.4 Product ecodesign, will consider two complementary points of view: on the one hand, the study of legislation, standards and literature relating to the ecodesign of the sectors, products and materials under study in GRAPHERGIA; on the other hand, a detailed study of the components and materials of the products developed in the project. All technical partners are required to provide information regarding components, materials, and their technical characteristics (such as the type of materials,

relative percentages of use within the total object, presence of hazardous chemicals, recyclability, etc.).

5.2.2 Key Applications piloted in three demo cases

GRAPHERGIA's demo cases are set to start piloting in March 2026 (M30), with preparatory work already underway for the involved partners. The demo cases are managed within the work packages 5 “Design, manufacturing and testing of representative technology” (lead by ADA). The demo cases are built with direct interaction with the target end-users (e.g., industry experts, technology providers and customers), collecting direct feedback (related notably to market needs, emerging opportunities, technical requirements etc.) and supporting the further definition of the KER exploitation pathways (*in relation to tasks 7.2 Exploitation and 7.3 IPR Management*).

Table 19 Demo Case #1 Overview

Demo Case #1: All-in-one self-charging textile capable of energy harvesting and storage	
Leading partner	Born
Involved partners	FORTH, ADA, PLE, UGE, URM, DLR, NTT, ComS
KER involved	KER#1, KER#3, KER#4, KER#5, and KER#6
<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>DEMO 1 ALL-IN-ONE SELF-CHARGING TEXTILE CAPABLE OF ENERGY HARVESTING AND STORAGE</p> <p>Diagram illustrating the components of Demo Case #1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laser Roll-2-Roll Graphene on Textiles High-Voltage Plasma Switch 4 e-Textiles KineticMesh Shelf-Charging IoT-enabled Power Textile Plasma-Enhanced Chemical Organic Coatings on Graphene FlexiGel-Micro-Super Capacitors 4 e-Textiles <p>GRAPHERGIA</p> </div>	
<p>Objective</p> <p>To develop and validate an all-in-one, wearable or upholstery-integrated self-powered textile system that combines energy harvesting and storage. Five KERs (as shown in the image above) will be involved in Demo #1.</p>	

Summary

Born, leveraging their TRL 9 expertise in e-textiles, will contribute their substantial experience in the validation and development of TENG-embedded textile demonstrators. They will further advance this innovation beyond the GRAPHERGIA project’s timeline, focusing on scaling, user acceptability, and integration into commercial textile products.

This demo considers two case studies. The first one (CS1) referred to smart clothing, a TENG structure that will be integrated, e.g. in a T-shirt for energy/ storage harvesting (CS1A) and on a belt for online gait monitoring (CS1B). The second (CS2) one referred to a smart-seat prototype, which will be tested as a self-powered passenger seat indicator.

Table 20 Demo Case #2 Overview

Demo Case #2: Self-powered structurally integrated sensor for aerospace structures	
Leading partner	ADA
Involved partners	FORTH, Born, PLE, UGE, URM, DLR, NTT, ComS
KER involved	KER#1 and KER#7

Objective

To design, fabricate, and structurally integrate a miniaturised TENG-powered wireless strain/temperature sensor into aerospace composite materials. Two KERs (as shown in the image above) will be involved in Demo #2.

Summary

ADA will subcontract CFRP material testing services to assess the impact of integrating the self-powered sensor into aerospace composite structures. Commercial validation will focus on ensuring that the sensor meets requirements for structural integrity, weight, and reliability. It will pilot the wireless miniaturised triboelectric nanogenerator-based strain sensor (which will enable accurate data) at the composite structure. The dimensions of the final demonstrator’s case studies are not yet finalized.

Table 21 Demo Case #3 Overview

Demo Case #3: Advanced graphene-based LIB modules for space deployment	
Leading partner	PLE
Involved partners	ADA, FORTH, NTT
KER involved	KER#2 and KER#8

DEMO 3

ADVANCED GRAPHENE-BASED LIB
MODULE PROTOTYPE FOR SPACE APPLICATIONS

Objective
To construct and functionally validate a graphene-based lithium-ion battery module for space applications. Two KERs (as shown in the image above) will be involved in Demo #3.

Summary
Following successful technology outcomes in cylindrical cell batteries and system-level demonstrations involving the assembly of a power module for CubeSats, this demonstrator aims to achieve a rapid increase in Technology Readiness Level (TRL). The goal is to mature the technology sufficiently for in-orbit demonstration and validation, confirming its suitability for space applications and paving the way for commercialisation in the aerospace sector. A CubeSat battery module is being created. The battery module will comprise cylindrical 21700 cells, a battery management system (BMS), interconnectors,

structural supports, and, if necessary, thermal management components. The design of the demonstrator will be finalised during the activity, beginning at M30.

5.2.2.1 Stakeholders and Ecosystem Impacting Exploitation

The project exploitation plan is implemented internally within the GRAPHERGIA consortium, which comprises 11 partner organisations. They have defined the foreground and background IP-ownerships concerning all KERs. Furthermore, [the partners](#) are the ones who define the specific exploitation paths (e.g., commercial, technical or scientific) for each KERs beyond the GRAPHERGIA project duration.

In addition to internal activities, GRAPHERGIA actively engages with a broad ecosystem of external stakeholders during the demonstration and exploitation stages to ensure market relevance, industrial scalability, and user acceptance. These include:

Industrial Reference Group

This group follows regularly GRAPHERGIA's research progress and related results, especially through dedicated meetings. Its members, grounded in the industrial applications of the three target sectors, are regularly introduced to GRAPHERGIA's ongoing research progress, technical and scientific methodologies, pilot status, and envisaged exploitation paths. Upon this introduction, they are invited to provide insights and feedback.

The IRG scientific committee comprises four professionals (listed in Table 30). During the 2nd project year, the scientific committee's engagement is especially important, as the key steps of GRAPHERGIA's research are ongoing. The 3rd and last project year will involve additional members of the industrial sector to gather recommendations on the initial results from the pilots and on further industrial applications. For this latter group, already two industrial representatives, from smart textiles and batteries manufacturing sectors, have confirmed their support.

Table 22 Industrial Reference Group Scientific Members

Name	Organisation (Country)	Position	Interest in GRAPHERGIA
Cristina Giusca (on LinkedIn)	National Physical Laboratory (UK)	Principal Scientist	Metrology and validation of laser-grown graphene on textiles
Beatriz Alonso (on LinkedIn)	GRAPHENEA	R+D Manager	Graphene-enabled innovation
Benedetto Bozzini (on LinkedIn)	Politecnico di Milano	Professor	Electrochemical Materials Science, Battery Materials, synthesis of novel materials and electrochemical devices
Jörg Radnik (on LinkedIn)	The Federal Institute for Material Research and Testing, Berlin; and the competence centre nano@BAM	Senior Scientist for Surface and Thin Film Analysis & Leader of the standardisation and	The chemical analysis of nanostructured materials and standardisation / regularization aspects of the innovation.

		regulation task in the Graphene Flagship CSA.	
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This scientific IRG Group (A) gathered online for the 1st time on the 5th of November 2025 with the GRAPHERGIA consortium. Based on the initial presentation of the key research objectives and process to the four scientific IRG members (*Group A: Focus on scientific feedback, including Benedetto Bozzini, Jörg Radnik, Cristina Giusca and Beatriz Alonso*), the project has gathered (with an online questionnaire, Annex 4) **their first feedback regarding the value and novelties, processes, and sustainability aspects of GRAPHERGIA**. Also, each member was asked a few more specific questions related to their field of expertise.

To sum up, all members agreed that the novelty/importance of laser-assisted graphene for flexible electrodes/smart textiles is strong in their respective domains (averaging 4.25 out of 5 points). They reckon that conductive textiles use case looks the most viable in the short term, followed by LIB anode foils. Micro-flexible supercapacitors and energy-harvesting devices (TENGs) share third place in the rating. Also, one member underlines the viability of interconnects for flexible electronics and sensors. All members fostered the importance of involving Battery/cell and supercapacitor manufacturers and Smart-textile manufacturers to validate market fit, manufacturability, and regulatory readiness; furthermore, 50% of them considered it relevant to involve device OEMs / Tier-1 integrators (wearables, IoT, energy storage) and materials producers (graphene, conductive coatings).

To lower the risk of scale-up inline metrology(ies), the members rated machine vision for track defects (rated at 2.5) as the top, followed by Raman mapping for graphene quality (ID/IG, 2D band shape, etc.) and Sheet-R mapping.

Moreover, in terms of sustainability, the solvent-free, single-step laser-assisted approach of GRAPHERGIA for scale-up was considered highly compelling (scoring 4.5 out of 5 on average). They also recommended collecting early evidence EHS risks (Environment, Health, Safety) risks, especially on worker exposure and end-of-life separation. Finally, regarding the LCA quantification metrics, it is recommended to deploy the following three: energy per unit area, CO₂ per unit area, and recyclability route. The detailed questions are included in **Erreur! Source du renvoi introuvable..**

GRAPHENE Flagship Initiative's Working Groups

GFi runs several working groups supporting the exploitation of the research and innovation projects, and GRAPHERGIA participates actively in these groups, feeding the most important results towards the relevant work packages, especially WP7.

- **Dissemination working group:** AUS represents the project in this WG that meets online with a regular basis. The aim of the group is to coordinate and collaborate within the GFi

communication and dissemination activities, supporting the impact of the running projects. This work group has annual highlights, especially Graphene Week events and Graphene Flagship annual reports.

- **Standardisation working group:** FORTH represents the project in this WG led by Jörg Radnik, also a member of the project’s scientific industrial reference group.
- **Innovation roadmap working group:** The Graphene Flagship Roadmap Working Group (RWG) brings together representatives from multiple projects to guide the upscaling of graphene from laboratory research to industrial application across Europe. Its main goal is to map and structure the technological pathways required for the large-scale adoption of graphene-enabled products. The RWG focuses on key sectors with the highest potential impact, such as composites and coatings, energy generation and storage, electronics and photonics, and biomedical applications, while setting clear development milestones. It also prioritises standardisation, sustainable large-scale production, and stronger coordination between research and industry. Overall, the RWG provides a realistic timeline for advancing graphene technologies toward commercialisation, aligned with the EU’s vision for innovation in advanced materials. ADA represents GRAPHERGIA in this group.
 - **Current Status:** The RWG now serves as the central reference for graphene industrialisation in Europe. While graphene’s scientific potential is proven, its large-scale adoption remains limited by challenges in cost-effective production, reproducibility, and quality certification. The RWG is working to advance graphene from the proof-of-concept stage to pre-commercial deployment, with current bottlenecks focused more on manufacturing and standardization than on scientific understanding. Towards this end, each entity partaking in the RWG is encouraged to deliver recurring updates in market, industrial and financial regards.
 - **Next Steps:** The next phase of the roadmap centers on stronger industrial alignment, scalable and sustainable production, and harmonized material standards across Europe. The RWG prioritizes standardization, metrology, and pilot-line development to validate graphene’s performance in real-world environments. The roadmap will continue to evolve with new data on technology readiness, industrial feedback, and market trends to maintain alignment with EU sustainability and competitiveness goals. Within this framework, GRAPHERGIA delivered its preliminary roadmap input in July 2025 and will submit the final version in December 2025. From March to June 2026, it will take part in the integration and review stages, contributing to the consolidated Graphene Flagship roadmap, which will be delivered to the European Commission in September 2026.

5.3 GRAPHERGIA’s target markets overview

Based on the definition of the key exploitable results and the three demo cases, as well as inputs gathered from the consortium’s exploitation partners and relevant stakeholders, the GRAPHERGIA project has assembled a landscape of its target markets, where outstanding gaps and challenges create opportunities for novel solutions.

The GRAPHERGIA project seeks to transform energy solutions through sustainable, efficient power technologies. It focuses on developing eco-friendly “dry electrode” fabrication for energy storage devices, leveraging the potential of lasers in graphene synthesis. Through the development of a novel process for laser-assisted synthesis, functionalisation, and integration of graphene materials into electrodes, with applications piloted in three key areas: energy-autonomous smart textiles, Li-ion batteries for space applications and strain/temperature sensors for aviation systems. These three segments are GRAPHERGIA's primary target markets for its innovation.

Figure 25: GRAPHERGIA's target markets

In addition, as a complement to the target markets, the project focuses on micro-flexible supercapacitors that can be applied across all three target sectors: smart textiles, the aerospace sensor sector, and spatial applications of energy storage systems. This work is led by DLR in the framework of KER#4 and can be considered a complementary element for commercialisation within the market analysis.

5.3.1 Smart e-textiles

Electronic textiles, or e-textiles, refer to textiles that incorporate electronic components, enabling functionalities such as sensing, heating, lighting, or data transmission. In this sense, smart clothing, also known as high-tech clothing, smart wear, electronic textiles, or smart fabrics, is designed to monitor the wearer's health by providing biometric information such as heart rate, body temperature, muscle tension, and pulse rate. GRAPHERGIA aspires to achieve one-step, laser-assisted synthesis, processing, functionalisation and integration of graphene-based materials into energy storage devices, aiming to revolutionise smart textiles. Self-charging textiles with integrated electronic systems (triboelectric nanogenerators, TENGs) will be used for biomechanical

energy harvesting. The project aims to make the charge-as-you-go lifestyle a reality for everyone, steering towards battery-free charging and enhanced IoT connectivity.

The global E-textile market was valued at **€2,73 million in 2023** and is projected to reach **€4,84 million by 2030**, at a **compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 8.4% during the forecast period**⁸. The e-textile market is experiencing steady growth, driven by technological advancements, the expanding use of e-textiles across industries, and growing interest in intelligent and wearable devices.

5.3.2 Advanced Lithium Ion (Li-Ion) batteries

Across Europe, following the Battery 2030+ roadmap⁹, the research actions to radically transform the way we discover, develop, and design ultra-high-performance, durable, safe, sustainable, and affordable batteries for use in real applications. GRAPHERGIA follows the roadmap principles by developing a credible and graphene-enabled dry electrode approach to fabricate next-generation LIB cells. In this sector, the project aims to develop a piloted process for a scalable, cost-effective, and climate-neutral production line for advanced Li-ion batteries.

Before looking into the specific market of Li-ion batteries applied in aerospace and space applications, it's relevant to understand the rapid evolution of the Li-ion battery markets in general. The projections highlight a robust upward trend in the European and global lithium-ion battery market, driven by increasing demand for electric vehicles, renewable energy storage solutions, and advancements in battery technology. **The European Li-Ion battery market is estimated to grow from €19.73 billion in 2025 to €32,15 billion in 2030 at a CAGR of 10.26% over this period**¹⁰

Moreover, GRAPHERGIA targets two key segments of the Li-Ion battery market, including aerospace and space applications. **Lithium-ion Batteries for Aerospace Market** stood at € 1.1 Billion in 2024 and is forecast to achieve €3.22 billion by 2033, registering a **12.5% CAGR from 2026 to 2033**¹¹. The same trend in growth can be expected for space applications; the space battery market, particularly lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries, is anticipated to grow substantially in the coming years, driven by the increasing number of satellite launches and advancements in space exploration technologies. **Space Battery Market size was valued at €1.57 billion in 2023 and is poised to grow from € 1.68 billion in 2024 to € 2.67 billion by 2032, growing at a CAGR of 7.10% during the forecast period (2025-2032)**¹². Overall, the aerospace and space sectors' increasing

⁸ <https://semiconductorinsight.com/report/e-textile-market/> (consulted 28/01/2025)

⁹ <https://battery2030.eu/research/roadmap/> (consulted 07/04/2025)

¹⁰ <https://www.knowledge-sourcing.com/report/europe-lithium-ion-li-ion-battery-market> (Consulted April 2025)

¹¹ <https://www.verifiedmarketreports.com/product/lithium-ion-batteries-for-aerospace-market/> (consulted 07/04/2025)

¹² <https://www.skyquestt.com/report/space-battery-market> (consulted 07/04/2025)

reliance on lithium-ion batteries, driven by technological advancements and sustainability goals, is expected to propel market expansion through 2030.

Strain and Temperature Sensors for Aerospace

GRAPHERGIA designs a sensor that is structurally integrated, meaning it can be embedded directly into aviation structures like wings or fuselages, and self-powered, harvesting its own energy rather than relying on batteries or wiring. This sensor measures strain (e.g., to detect deformation, stress, or potential fatigue in structural components) and temperature (e.g., to monitor thermal conditions that may affect material performance) in aviation structures, enabling real-time monitoring of structural integrity and conditions without external power sources. This results to a key exploitable result (KER#7) and it is piloted in the demo case #2.

With regards to the related market insights, overall aerospace Sensor Market size is estimated to be 7.2 billion euros in 2026 and is expected to reach 10.5 billion euros by 2033 at a **CAGR of 4.5% from 2026 to 2033**. North America leads this sector with the highest market share at 38%, followed by Europe (30%), Asia Pacific (25%)¹³. Linked with this, the global temperature sensors market size was estimated to grow at a CAGR of 6.0% from 2024 to 2030. The market growth is due to rising applications of temperature sensors and growth in the electronics sector and the Asia Pacific region was the largest market in 2023¹⁴. Moreover, the market growth is expected to be similar for the Strain Gauge Market. The market size is estimated to evolve at a CAGR of 5.1% from 2026 to 2033.

Globally, the rise of smart sensors, which incorporate advanced features such as wireless connectivity, data analytics, and machine learning capabilities. Smart sensors enhance the traditional role of strain gauges, offering real-time data and insights that improve decision-making processes in industries like aerospace and construction. These innovations support the growing trend of Industry 4.0, where automation and data exchange are critical for efficiency and productivity. As businesses continue to invest in these technologies, the demand for stain / temperature is expected to surge.

5.4 E-textile market insights and challenges

5.4.1 Smart textiles market insights

The key applications of e-textiles cover¹⁵:

- **Healthcare:** High demand for patient monitoring and rehabilitation garments supported by advanced healthcare systems, especially in North America and Europe. The healthcare

¹³ <https://www.verifiedmarketreports.com/product/aerospace-sensor-market> (consulted September 2025)

¹⁴ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/temperature-sensors-market>

¹⁵ <https://semiconductorinsight.com/report/e-textile-market/> (consulted 28/01/2025)

segment for e-textiles is projected to grow at a CAGR of 18% from 2024 to 2030, driven by advancements in medical technology and the need for continuous patient monitoring.

- **Military and Defense:** Used for real-time performance monitoring, camouflage, and communication, this segment is expected to grow at a CAGR of 15% from 2024 to 2030
- **Sports and Fitness:** Adoption of biometric monitoring garments and performance-tracking wearables is strong, with a growth rate of around 13% CAGR
- **Fashion and Entertainment:** E-textiles are increasingly used for interactive designs, dynamic clothing, and theatrical applications, with a CAGR of 12%.

Regarding regional insights, in 2023, North America leads with a 38% market share, driven by high R&D investments and strong demand across healthcare and military applications¹⁶. Asia Pacific is estimated to be the most opportunistic market during the forecast period. The government's rising expenditure in the military, aerospace, and healthcare industries in countries like China and India presents immense growth opportunities for market players.

Europe represents around 30% of the worldwide e-textiles market, with demand primarily driven by the healthcare, sports, and automotive industries¹⁷. Germany, the United Kingdom, and France drive the region, benefiting from strong industries that incorporate e-textiles for applications ranging from patient monitoring to automotive comfort and safety. Germany, with its strong textile and automotive sectors, actively integrates smart textiles for real-time vehicle monitoring and wearable health solutions. The U.K. and France see strong growth in e-textile wearables, particularly in fitness and sports, as consumers increasingly seek tech-integrated fitness gear.

5.4.2 Challenges for Smart Textile Markets

There are several key barriers¹⁸ in the e-textile markets, including:

- **High production costs:** E-textiles involve sophisticated components, including sensors, conductive threads, and microprocessors, which raise production costs. Integrating these electronics into fabrics requires specialised manufacturing processes, making e-textiles more expensive than conventional fabrics. The U.S. Department of Commerce has noted that the need for high-quality, durable electronic components to ensure functionality significantly reduces costs, deterring smaller companies from entering the market and restricting mass adoption.
- **Technical challenges with durability and flexibility:** Ensuring that e-textiles remain durable, flexible, and washable over long periods poses a considerable challenge. Embedding electronic components that can withstand regular wear and washing cycles without degrading is complex. According to the European Commission, durability issues impact the market as manufacturers strive to balance electronic performance with fabric flexibility.

¹⁶ <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/e-textiles-market> (consulted 28/01/2025)

¹⁷ <https://www.credenceresearch.com/report/e-textiles-market> (consulted 28/01/2025)

¹⁸ <https://www.credenceresearch.com/report/e-textiles-market> (consulted 28/01/2025)

The lack of standard testing protocols for e-textiles' durability also creates inconsistencies in product quality across regions and suppliers, affecting consumer trust.

- **Regulatory and safety concerns:** E-textiles fall under textile and electronic regulations, requiring compliance with multiple standards. This complexity creates regulatory barriers for manufacturers aiming to meet both product safety and electronic standards across regions. In Europe, the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) regulates chemical use in textile manufacturing. Complying with these regulations is costly and time-intensive, particularly for smaller firms, and inhibits faster product development and market entry.
- **Limited consumer awareness and market penetration:** Despite growing interest, consumer awareness of e-textiles remains limited. Many consumers are unfamiliar with the functionalities of e-textiles, which reduces demand. Additionally, there is a lack of understanding about smart fabrics among the general public, underscoring the need for educational initiatives. Limited awareness hinders the market's growth potential.
- **Complex supply chains:** Obtaining the right materials for producing e-textiles and then getting them to customers can be labour-intensive and take time. Challenges or delays in any section of this process may affect output and lead to rising costs. These problems can make it hard for companies to fulfil their delivery plans, affecting their sales and market reputation¹⁹.

5.5 Li-ion battery market insights and challenges

Beyond the smart textile market, the GRAPHERGIA solution considers the drivers and challenges of Li-ion battery markets for space and aerospace applications, which contribute to defining its market positioning and added value.

5.5.1 Drivers of the Li-ion battery and the target sub-markets

In general terms, the advanced Li-ion Batteries' market growth is driven by several key factors, including:

- **Electric Vehicles (EVs):** The global shift towards sustainable transportation has led to a surge in EV adoption, necessitating high-performance batteries. Advanced lithium-ion batteries are preferred for their superior energy density and efficiency²⁰.
- **Technological and technical advancements:** Ongoing research focuses on enhancing battery performance, including improvements in energy density, charging speed, and

¹⁹ <https://www.globalmarketstatistics.com/market-reports/e-textile-market-12042> (consulted 28/01/2025)

²⁰ www.marketresearchfuture.com/reports/advanced-lithium-ion-batteries-market-10123?utm (consulted on 07/04/2025)

lifespan, making advanced lithium-ion batteries more appealing across various applications²¹.

- **Renewable energy integration:** The increasing deployment of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, requires efficient energy storage systems to manage supply and demand, thereby bolstering the need for advanced lithium-ion batteries.

In terms of regional considerations, the Asia-Pacific region dominates the market, driven by its role as a global manufacturing hub and the rapid adoption of EVs, particularly in countries such as China and Japan. Whereas, North America and Europe are experiencing significant growth due to supportive government policies promoting clean energy and the increasing adoption of EVs.

GRAPHERGIA's next-gen Li-Ion battery innovation is being piloted for space applications (demo 3), and it will be further implemented in relevant space applications. In this sense, GRAPHERGIA reckons that space and aerospace batteries are becoming an important part of space missions, airborne remote sensing programs, and defence and security applications.

Firstly, looking into GRAPHERGIA's sub target market of batteries for aerospace applications, **the key drivers²² of the growth of aerospace** include:

- **Electrification of aviation systems:** The shift towards electric and hybrid-electric aviation necessitates lightweight, high-energy-density batteries.
- **Technological advancements:** Continuous improvements in battery technologies, such as solid-state batteries and enhanced thermal management systems, are enhancing performance and safety. The development of safer, more reliable and higher energy density batteries fit the aerospace industry requirements. Also, lithium-ion batteries are presently the topmost choice in the field of space batteries because of their characteristics such as high energy density and lightweight.
- **Environmental sustainability initiatives:** The aerospace industry's focus on reducing carbon emissions is accelerating the adoption of electric propulsion systems powered by advanced batteries.
- **Surge in satellite deployments:** The rapid increase in satellite launches for communication, navigation, and Earth observation purposes necessitates reliable and efficient power sources, boosting the demand for advanced batteries.

Overall, the aerospace sector's increasing reliance on lithium-ion batteries, is driven by technological advancements and sustainability goals, is expected to propel market expansion through 2030. The new gen battery markets are essentially driven by technological and technical

²¹ / www.gminsights.com/industry-analysis/lithium-ion-battery-market utm (consulted on 07/04/2025)

²² <https://markwideresearch.com/lithium-ion-batteries-for-aerospace-market/> (consulted September 2025)

advancements, enlarging their application areas. However, these markets have several outstanding social, economic and political challenges, which are GRAPHERGIA's research.

5.5.2 Challenges faced in the Lithium-ion battery market

A joint 2023 report by McKinsey and the Global Battery Alliance (GBA) “Battery 2030: Resilient, sustainable, and circular”²³, shares a Li-ion battery demand forecast providing revenue opportunities for over 338 billion Euro by 2023. However, the report highlights a set of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) challenges the battery supply chain faces, which require novel solutions.

- **Supply chain constraints and raw material dependency:** the industry heavily relies on critical minerals like lithium, cobalt, nickel, manganese, and graphite, which are essentially sourced from a few geopolitically sensitive regions (e.g., the Democratic Republic of Congo, Chile, Argentina, and China). Moreover, China dominates the refining and processing of lithium, turning it into battery-grade chemicals.²⁴ This imbalance introduces risks, including price volatility, supply disruptions, and geopolitical leverage.
- **Environmental and ethical impacts on mining regions**²⁵: Extraction and processing of battery materials pose significant environmental threats—water depletion, toxic pollution, habitat degradation, and substantial CO₂ emissions. Lithium extraction increases water usage in arid regions, impacting indigenous lands. For instance, lithium mining in Chile’s Atacama consumes excessive water, stirring local conflicts. Also, release of chemicals and heavy metals from mining can pollute water sources. Moreover, mining operations can disrupt ecosystems and lead to long-term land degradation which also impacts the indigenous rights. Also, severe human rights issues are identified, including violation of labor laws, child and forced labour in several mines.
- **Bottlenecks in manufacturing and production scaling:** Ramping up production capacity is challenging due to equipment shortages, lack of skilled labour, and limited manufacturing infrastructure, particularly in Europe.²⁶
- **Limits in recycling and end-of-life management:** Recycling infrastructure is underdeveloped. Shortages in recycled feedstock (“black mass”) are disrupting operations globally, especially in Europe and Asia.²⁷ Growing volumes of end-of-life batteries exacerbate environmental and sustainability challenges, and therefore battery manufacturers should focus on developing and maintaining battery quality, which has important impacts on questions around battery reuse and recycling.²⁸

²³ <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/automotive-and-assembly/our-insights/battery-2030-resilient-sustainable-and-circular> (consulted September 2025)

²⁴ <https://energy.sustainability-directory.com/question/why-are-critical-minerals-geopolitically-sensitive/>

²⁵ <https://energy.sustainability-directory.com/question/what-are-ethical-concerns-surrounding-battery-materials/> (consulted September 2025)

²⁶ <https://www.impomag.com/inventory-management/article/22871587/keeping-the-battery-supply-chain-flowing>

²⁷ <https://www.fastmarkets.com/insights/lithium-ion-battery-recycling-feedstock-shortage/>

²⁸ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666386424003011>

- **Safety, quality control and counterfeit risks:** The surge of substandard or counterfeit batteries poses quality and safety issues, highlighting the need for better authentication and manufacturing controls. Lithium-ion batteries are prone to thermal runaway and fires.²⁹ the battery industry has already experienced both highly-visible safety incidents and under-the-radar reliability issues, a trend that will only worsen if left unaddressed.³⁰
- **Uncertain market dynamics and industry consolidation in Europe:** Fierce competition and price wars pressure battery manufacturers, cutting back innovation, sustainability and quality. Many battery producers in Europe are postponing or cancelling expansion plans because of uncertainty about future profitability.³¹

The two sub-markets face challenges identified above, including their own specificities as follows. With a focus on **the aerospace and space markets, these face the following challenges:**³²

- **Complying with safety and certification:** Ensuring battery reliability and meeting stringent aerospace safety standards are critical concerns. Even more, to withstand the harsh conditions of space, batteries must meet rigorous standards for reliability, durability, and safety.
- **High production costs and scalability:** High production costs of li-ion batteries, covering raw materials and manufacturing processes combined with scalability issues may hinder widespread market adoption.

5.6 Aviation sensor market insights and challenges

The aviation sensor market includes several types of sensors, including fibre-optic, MEMS/microelectromechanical, and strain and temperature measurement sensors. GRAPHERGIA's sensor solution is integrated into the aviation structure (e.g., a blade) and measures both temperature and strain.

These sensors are serving for different monitoring purposes:

- **Structural Health Monitoring (SHM):** wings, fuselage, control surfaces, landing gear fatigue monitoring.
- **Engine and propulsion monitoring:** turbine temperatures, causing strain.
- **Environmental and thermal control:** avionic racks, battery systems, thermal management in satellites.

²⁹ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.03607>

³⁰ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-025-55861-7>

³¹ <https://www.iea.org/commentaries/the-battery-industry-has-entered-a-new-phase>

³² <https://markwideresearch.com/lithium-ion-batteries-for-aerospace-market/>

5.6.1 Drivers of the aviation sensor market³³

- **Adoption of SHM and predictive maintenance (PDM):** airlines want condition-based maintenance to lower life-cycle costs and increase aviation availability – this drives demand for permanent strain/temperature sensor installations and data analytics.
- **Composites and new airframe designs:** composite structures need distributed sensing (FBG, distributed fiber) because classical strain-gauge placement is less effective.
- **Electrification and thermal management:** more electric aviation, battery systems and electrified subsystems increase the need for precise temperature monitoring.

5.6.2 Key challenges of the aviation sensor market

- **Harsh environment qualification:** sensors for aerospace/space must meet vibration, shock, radiation (space), vacuum, thermal cycling and long-life specifications. Therefore, certification is lengthy and expensive.
- **Integration and wiring complexity:** distributed sensors (many nodes) require lightweight cabling or data concentrators; integration and weight penalties can be an obstacle.
- **Data handling and cyber threats:** SHM creates large data volumes; customers require validated algorithms and trusted diagnostics. As aerospace sensors become more interconnected through IoT and other digital platforms, they are also more susceptible to cyber threats, necessitating robust security measures to safeguard sensitive data and systems.
- **Increase in operational costs:** One significant issue is the rapid pace of technological change, which requires companies to continually innovate and upgrade their product offerings to remain competitive. This creates pressure on research and development budgets and can lead to increased operational costs.

5.7 PESTEL Analysis

PESTEL analysis is a strategic tool used to assess an organisation's external environment. It examines six key factors: Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal. Considering these factors, organisations can identify opportunities and threats and develop strategies to adapt to the changing landscape. Through the PESTEL analysis, the GRAPHERGIA project has gained a comprehensive understanding of its external environment and developed strategies to thrive in the European markets, combining its applications linked with smart textile, next-generation Li-ion battery and aviation sensor markets.

5.7.1 PESTEL Analysis - Smart Textiles Sector

The smart textile market is positioned at the crossroads of textiles, electronics, and healthcare. Opportunities exist in health monitoring, sports, defence, and fashion, but challenges persist

³³ <https://advanced.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/adem.202401745?af=R>

regarding high costs, regulation, and sustainability. Long-term success depends on scaling production, ensuring data privacy, and aligning with sustainability goals.

Figure 26: PESTEL Overview of Smart Textile sector

POLITICAL

- **Government funding and innovation policies:** Many governments support R&D in advanced materials, IoT, and health monitoring technologies, which encourages the development of smart textiles. GRAPHERGIA's partners, including key SMEs and research institutes, are well-positioned for the EU innovation programme in the sector.
- **Defence and military demand:** Strong government interest in smart textiles for protective clothing, soldier monitoring, and camouflage systems. GRAPHERGIA's demo case 1 could be further applied to the military markets.
- **Trade policies and tariffs:** GRAPHERGIA can leverage trade agreements to expand its reach into new markets and facilitate cross-border data flows. While it should consider that international supply chains (especially in textiles and electronics) are affected by tariffs, export controls, and regional trade agreements.
- **Regulation of health and safety:** Smart textiles used in medical applications must comply with healthcare device regulations. In case of further application in the health device sector, GRAPHERGIA should ensure compliance.

ECONOMIC

- **Rising consumer purchasing power:** Demand for premium fitness, fashion, and wellness products is growing, creating significant opportunities for GRAPHERGIA to capitalise on.

- **High production costs:** Integration of electronics into textiles increases costs, limiting mass adoption, which GRAPHERGIA needs to consider in its business model.
- **Global economic fluctuations:** Slowdowns can impact discretionary spending on wearable tech, whilst investments in defence and military tech are increasing, creating the most interesting economic opportunities to GRAPHERGIA.
- **Cost of raw materials and semiconductors:** Dependence on both textile and electronics supply chains exposes the sector to price volatility, which GRAPHERGIA will consider, especially in risk management.

SOCIAL

- **Health and wellness awareness:** Growing demand for smart textiles that monitor biometrics, posture, and physical performance. GRAPHERGIA validated the created IoT (Internet of Things)-enabled self-powered textile system that combines energy harvesting and storage.
- **The ageing European population:** Demand for healthcare monitoring textiles (e.g., heart rate, temperature) is rising, presenting a major market opportunity for GRAPHERGIA.
- **Consumer acceptance and privacy concerns:** Some consumers remain hesitant due to data privacy risks and usability challenges, which GRAPHERGIA will consider as engaging further with target end-user groups as part of its validation.

TECHNOLOGICAL

- **Advances in IoT and sensor technologies:** Decrease in sensor sizes and flexible electronics make integration with textiles easier. GRAPHERGIA develops a TENG-system (tribo-electric nano-generator) power management circuits for e-textiles
- **Fabrics for energy harvesting and storage:** Progress in lightweight, washable batteries and energy-harvesting fabrics is critical. GRAPHERGIA deploys TENGs that are miniature devices able to harvest mechanical energy (friction at the nanoscale) and convert it to electricity.
- **Upscaling solutions with artificial intelligence and data analytics:** These technologies enable meaningful insights from biometric data collected via smart clothing, which could be embedded into the GRAPHERGIA system.
- **Manufacturing innovation:** GRAPHERGIA has an experienced project SME partner invested in 3D knitting, conductive fibres, and nanotechnology. Notably, their expertise is utilised in manufacturing processes, which is a factor that reduces costs and enhances durability.
- **Interoperability challenges:** Ensuring compatibility across devices and ecosystems is still an obstacle that GRAPHERGIA's solution will also face.

ENVIRONMENTAL

- **Sustainability pressure and climate change awareness:** GRAPHERGIA reckons that the textile industry is scrutinised for environmental impact, creating demand for eco-friendly smart textiles and using greener resources in the manufacturing process.

- **Electronic waste concerns:** Integrating electronics into fabrics raises recycling and disposal challenges, which GRAPHERGIA considers as part of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) process.
- **Regulations on chemical use:** Stricter rules on dyes, coatings, and materials affect production choices that GRAPHERGIA is also committed to.

LEGAL

- **Intellectual property (IP) protection:** Patent disputes around wearable technology and sensor integration are common. Strong intellectual property protection can help GRAPHERGIA to safeguard its innovations and compete effectively in the market.
- **Medical device regulations:** Smart textiles used for diagnostics or monitoring must comply with FDA/EMA standards, which GRAPHERGIA will consider in its business model specification.
- **Data protection laws:** GRAPHERGIA will comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and European national privacy laws in case it implements a model for storing and sharing biometric data from textiles.
- **Workplace safety laws:** Adoption in industries (construction, mining, army, etc.) requires compliance with safety certification standards that GRAPHERGIA would consider for further application areas.

5.7.2 PESTEL Analysis – Li-Ion Batteries in Aerospace & Space Applications

Aerospace Li-ion batteries provide essential power solutions for a wide range of applications, including aviation, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), satellites, and defence systems, which are all considered as part of the PESTEL analysis of this sub-market³⁴. This analysis of these two submarkets shares some similarities (both need safety, reliability, and certification), but space adds harsher operating environments, different political drivers, and unique economic and technological factors.

³⁴ <https://dataintelo.com/report/aerospace-lithium-ion-battery-market>

Figure 27: PESTEL Overview of LIB sector

POLITICAL

- **National defence programs:** National defence budgets (U.S. DoD, ESA, NASA, JAXA) heavily influence funding for aerospace-grade batteries.
- **Strategic autonomy:** EU Governments push for domestic aerospace supply chains (EU & U.S. want to reduce reliance on Chinese batteries).
- **Aviation-specific regulations:** GRAPHERGIA acknowledges that the aerospace market operators must comply with aviation-specific regulations (overseen by EASA).
- **Public procurement policies:** Military and aerospace programs fund battery research and development, making government contracts a critical component also for further applications of GRAPHERGIA.

ECONOMIC

- **Market growth:** GRAPHERGIA positions itself in the aerospace batteries market, which is a niche, specialised, and more expensive production segment compared to Electric Vehicles (EVs) or consumer cells. Projections show a CAGR of ~12% (2026–2033), but absolute volumes are small compared to EV/energy storage markets.
- **High value, low volume:** Both markets are low-scale, high-margin, very different from Electric Vehicles (EV) markets.
- **Budget sensitivity:** Demand is tied to government budgets and space missions rather than consumer demand. Space projects often face delays due to funding cycles.
- **Risk of overdependence:** Small supplier base; disruption at a single specialised manufacturer can ripple across the industry.

- **Government contracts:** Much demand comes from military aviation, making public budgets key economic drivers (such as the European Satellite Agency or European Defence Fund programmes) also for GRAPHERGIA's applications.

SOCIAL

- **Safety-critical perception of users:** Passenger trust in electric/hybrid aviation depends on flawless battery reliability. GRAPHERGIA understands that there is a zero tolerance for fire risks.
 - **Aerospace:** Passenger confidence in hybrid aviation depends on zero-failure battery performance.
 - **Space:** Mission success depends on flawless reliability, where battery failure can jeopardise multi-billion-dollar satellites.
- **ESG pressure:** Stakeholders expect ethical sourcing of raw materials, fair labour practices, and reduced carbon footprints across supply chains which also guides GRAPHERGIA's Li-ion battery module development process.

TECHNOLOGICAL

- **Critical reliability:** Batteries must operate in a vacuum, under extreme temperatures, and under strict redundancy requirements.
- **Advanced chemistries:** Strong interest in solid-state, lithium-sulfur, and silicon anodes to improve energy density and safety
- **Lightweighting:** Space and aerospace batteries prioritise high energy-to-weight ratios, which is also a guiding principle in GRAPHERGIA battery module development.
- **Digitalisation:** AI-based monitoring and predictive maintenance for in-flight and in-orbit battery management.

ENVIRONMENTAL³⁵

- **Environmental impact on Earth:** Decarbonization of aviation aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions through the use of sustainable fuels, innovative technologies, and optimised operations. Whereas the space applications have a limited direct environmental impact on Earth (due to small production volumes). These can even indirectly support sustainability through Earth-observation satellites that track climate change.
- **Limited mining impact:** Aerospace uses far fewer raw materials than EVs, but still depends on lithium, cobalt, and nickel.
- **Very low recycling rates:** Most space batteries are never recovered after orbit

LEGAL³⁶

³⁵ <https://www.itf-oecd.org/decarbonising-aviation>

³⁶ <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/the-agency/faqs/lithium-batteries>

- **Certification standards:** Batteries must comply with FAA, EASA, NASA, and MIL-SPEC requirements – some of the strictest technical regulations in the world. Whereas space applications must comply with NASA, ESA, JAXA qualification for orbital/space conditions.
- **Safety compliance:** Laws cover flammability, pressure changes, vibration, and crashworthiness.
- **Space-Specific regulations:** Satellites and spacecraft batteries must meet radiation and vacuum endurance certifications.
- **Liability risks:** Any incident (e.g., battery fire in-flight) exposes manufacturers to severe legal consequences.

5.7.3 PESTEL Analysis: Strain/ Temperature sensor market

This market is directly influenced by public policies, especially via government budgets, regulations, and export controls. From the economical point of view, the certification costs and ROI pressure are major adoption barriers. Whereas, from the social perspective, safety and sustainability trends create long-term demand pull. Moreover, from the technological side, fiber-optics, wireless, MEMS, and AI analytics create the biggest opportunities for this target sector. Sensors play a key role in Structural Health monitoring (SHM) of aviation, which aligns with sustainability goals, as this enables predictive care models for the aerospace structures.³⁷

Figure 28: PESTEL Overview of Smart Sensor sector

POLITICAL

³⁷ <https://advanced.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/adem.202401745>

- **Defence and aerospace budgets:** National and supranational funding (e.g. US DoD, ESA, Horizon Europe, NASA) directly influence adoption of advanced sensors for structural health monitoring (SHM), avionics, and spacecraft.
- **Government incentives for aerospace R&D:** Many countries fund smart materials and sensor systems to maintain aerospace competitiveness.
- **Geopolitical tensions and export controls:** Restrictions on dual-use technologies, ITAR, and defense procurement rules can limit market access for foreign suppliers.
- **Space policy and sovereignty:** National ambitions (ESA, India, China, US Space Force) push demand for space-qualified sensors; domestic sourcing policies may restrict non-local vendor.

ECONOMIC

- **New aviation orders:** Demand for SHM sensors depends on new aviation orders; downturns (COVID-19, recessions) delay adoption.
- **High qualification and certification costs:** Long certification cycles drive up development cost and reduce ROI for small players.
- **Growing commercial space sector:** Lower launch costs (SpaceX, Rocket Lab) and mega constellations (Starlink, OneWeb) increase sensor volumes in spacecraft.
- **Cost sensitivity of operators:** Airlines and satellite integrators need clear payback from permanent monitoring; otherwise retrofit adoption is slow.
- **Supply chain volatility:** Shortages of specialized fiber-optic components, high-purity alloys, or semiconductor parts raise costs and delay deliveries.

SOCIAL

- **Safer and greener aviation:** Pressure to improve safety and reduce unplanned downtime supports adoption of predictive maintenance sensors.
- **Acceptance of new maintenance practices:** Airlines and regulators are moving toward condition-based maintenance (CBM), which relies heavily on strain and temperature data.
- **Growing awareness of sustainability:** Societal focus on reducing emissions makes efficient maintenance and SHM more attractive.
- **Workforce skills gap:** Sensor integration, fiber-optic installation, and data analytics require specialized training, which may lag adoption.

TECHNOLOGICAL

- **Wireless and energy harvesting sensors:** Reduce cabling complexity and retrofit costs, especially attractive for legacy fleets.
- **MEMS miniaturization:** Smaller, lighter sensors reduce weight and improve integration for UAVs and small sats.
- **Integration with AI/IoT:** Cloud-based analytics and digital twins convert sensor data into actionable maintenance insights.
- **Competing sensing technologies:** Non-contact methods (IR thermography, ultrasonic SHM) may substitute or complement strain/temperature sensors in some niches.

- **Space-hardening challenges:** Designing sensors to survive radiation, vacuum, and extreme thermal cycling remains a major technical barrier.

ENVIRONMENTAL

- **Sustainability and lifecycle emissions:** SHM-enabled predictive maintenance reduces resource use and emissions by avoiding unnecessary part replacements.
- **Climate change and extreme conditions:** Rising operating temperatures, humidity, and storm frequency increase the need for robust monitoring sensors.
- **End-of-life disposal and recycling:** Sensor materials (e.g. rare alloys, optical fibers, thermocouple materials) pose challenges in recycling and sustainability compliance.

LEGAL

- **Certification requirements:** FAA, EASA, and ECSS (space) impose strict qualification (vibration, thermal cycling, radiation) before sensors are accepted in critical systems.
- **Data ownership and cybersecurity laws:** Strain/temperature data may be considered safety-critical; storage, transmission, and analytics must meet data security regulations
- **Standards evolution:** New SHM guidelines from SAE, ASTM, or EASA could accelerate or slow adoption depending on how prescriptive they are.
- **Liability risks:** If a sensor fails and contributes to an accident or in-orbit anomaly, manufacturers may face significant legal exposure.
- **Export restrictions:** ITAR/EAR and EU dual-use regulations complicate global sales of aerospace sensors.

5.8 Competition Analysis

5.8.1 Key competitors in smart textiles

The European smart textile market is competitive, with a mix of established players and new entrants. Competitors vary widely in their capabilities, from XXX. Below are listed the main competitors based in Europe, their solutions in the e-textile domain³⁸:

1. Schoeller Textil AG (Switzerland)³⁹

Founded in 1868, a global player in high-tech and functional textiles. Schoeller expands further, securing the textile growth markets at the site through its own branches, joint venture participations, and strategic cooperations. Family-owned, with strong Swiss roots, emphasising precision, sustainability, and innovation. In 2020, the Taiwanese company Formosa Taffeta Co., Ltd., became a 50 % shareholder in Schoeller Textil AG via capital increase.

Schoeller sees itself as a system supplier with a strategic focus on e-textiles. Schoeller Textil AG focuses on the production of scalable e-textiles, including essentially:

³⁸ <https://www.maximizemarketresearch.com/market-report/global-smart-textile-market/28970/>

³⁹ <https://www.schoeller-textiles.com/en/>

- **The schoeller® E-soft-shell heating technology:** a heatable fabric lining with an integrated network of conductive yarns. As a part of a textile laminate, it can be bonded to an arbitrary outer material, usually in combination with our corkshell™ technology for additional thermal insulation.
- **The HYDRO_BOT® technology** from Osmotex enables active, electronically controllable water vapour transport.

Strengths: Long company history with Swiss precision, strong R&D, and investment in sustainability.

Weaknesses: Competing with specialised players in electronic integration (vs textile only), cost pressures vs lower-cost manufacturers, complexity and cost of smart component integration.

Opportunities: Growing demand in sustainably produced products.

Threats: Need to scale smart textile electronics integration; may lag in fully embedded sensing, washable e-textile systems compared to dedicated smart textile firms.

2. Interactive Wear AG (Germany)⁴⁰

The company emerged from the complete acquisition of Infineon Technologies AG's wearable electronics activities. Founded in 2005, headquartered in Starnberg. It is a leading provider of innovative smart textile solutions. The company specialises in developing and manufacturing high-tech textiles integrated with sensors, electronics, and software. The company's products are designed for various applications, including healthcare, sports, and entertainment, allowing the deployment of more than 130 commercialised wearable and smart textiles projects run in collaboration with diverse organisations. Examples include:

- **Heated mattress for patient transport:** A powerful mobile heating electronics combined with sensor-controlled heating pads is the core technology for AKMedTec's innovative product.
- **HAV-Sentry glove:** Co-developed a system to provide real-time alerts based on vibration perceived by the user's hand, preventing overexposure and driving the formation of robust control measures with the aim of improving workers' safety.

Strengths: well-placed as a technology enabler for brands seeking to integrate electronics into textiles. engineering know-how and prototyping-to-production support

Weaknesses: Growth depends on overcoming scalability and cost issues

Opportunities: Specialist in integrating electronics/sensors into textiles; strong in wearable systems, modular platforms; good reputation in R&D and for productizing smart fabrics.

Threats: competition from both niche rivals (, Nanoleq, etc.) and large brands (Adidas, Gore, DuPont) entering smart textiles, durability / washability challenges.

⁴⁰ <https://interactive-wear.de/>

3. Clothing+ (Jabil) (Finland)⁴¹

Clothing+ is a Finland-based pioneer in textile-integrated electronics (smart garments). It was acquired by electronics manufacturer Jabil in June 2015 and now operates as Jabil's smart-garment capability. It provides end-to-end smart-garment solutions: textile-integrated sensors (heart-rate, bioimpedance, stretch/strain), washable connectors/cabling, embedded electronics modules and reference designs to accelerate productisation. The company has helped major brands, including Adidas, Garmin, Salomon and Philips, achieve first-to-market status with highly differentiated smart textile products.

- **End-to-end smart-garment solutions:** textile-integrated sensors (heart-rate, bioimpedance, stretch/strain), washable connectors/cabling, embedded electronics modules and reference designs to accelerate productisation.
- **“Peak+”** reference-design approach bundles textile sensors + transmitter + analytics partners to shorten time-to-market.

Strengths: Fast scale-up on both European and US markets benefiting from merge with Jabil. Partnerships with sports, electronics and analytics firms

Weaknesses: integrating soft textiles and electronics at scale is technically and quality-control heavy

Opportunities: eHealth, and especially Clinical remote monitoring and telehealth. Clothing+ can leverage Jabil's ability to meet medical production and regulatory needs.

Threats: Especially medical applications require costly clinical validation and certification – time and expense risk for commercialisation.

4. Nanoleq (Switzerland)⁴²

a Swiss smart-textile / textile-computing specialist spun out of ETH Zürich, focused on textile-integrated biosensing and production-ready components. In Nov 2024 Nanoleq was acquired by Myant (a Toronto-headquartered textile-computing and healthcare textiles company) to expand Myant's EU/EMEA footprint and integrate Nanoleq's sensor tech into its health-textile portfolio.

- **ElectroSkin:** a silicone-based dry electrode designed for textile integration (thin, elastic, corrosion/sweat resistant, claimed to perform similarly or better than gel electrodes while being washable). It is positioned for medical-grade biosignal capture in garments.
- **PhantomTape / PhantomLink:** production-friendly components (adhesive/laminatable conductive tape and connection solutions) intended for high-throughput textile bonding and robust electrically conductive interfaces in garments. The company emphasises industrial producibility and washability.

⁴¹ <https://investors.jabil.com/news/news-details/2015/Jabil-and-Clothing-Introduce-Smart-Garment-Solution/default.aspx>

⁴² <https://www.nanoleq.com/>

- **Full solutions & manufacturing support:** Nanoleq supplies both components (electrodes, conductive tapes, cabling) and system integration know-how for medical, sports and workwear customers; they also offer testing protocols (wash, stretch, chemical resistance) to ensure robustness.

Strengths: Production readiness - their silicone dry electrodes and PhantomTape are developed with manufacturability (lamination, hot-press bonding) and washability in mind, reducing a common barrier to adoption

Weaknesses: Regulatory and validation burden, competition for components as conductive tapes/electrodes and textile connectors are a hot area

Opportunities: rising demand for remote patient monitoring, telehealth and occupational health wearables; integration into Myant's global product lines opens new channels.

Threats: rapid materials innovation (printed electrodes, graphene, PEDOT:PSS), low-cost competitors, and regulatory delays that slow commercialisation.

5.8.2 Key competitors of Li-ion batteries for space and aerospace applications

There are several key companies and organisations in Europe active in Li-ion battery supply for aerospace and space (space) applications, along with relevant evidence and some of their capabilities.

1. Saft (TotalEnergies) (France)⁴³

Long-standing heritage in aerospace and space. They design high-quality Li-ion batteries for airplanes, satellites, extreme environments, and mission-critical systems. Involved in European battery R&D consortia for aerospace applications.

- Li-ion aviation batteries: The aviation industry is moving towards hybrid and electric aviation as cleaner and more efficient alternatives to traditional engines. Li-ion technology is key to this transformation.
- Advanced batteries for space applications (Saft solution for LEO and small GEO applications, VL51ES battery, 4s1p VES16 battery etc.)

Strengths: Competitive advantage: proven track records of flight-heritage, qualification, and ability to meet ECSS / EASA / MIL standards. This is a major competitive advantage.

Weaknesses: High costs, low scalability, slower pace in next-gen chemistries, and reliance on government contracts.

Opportunities: Vertical Integration leveraging in-house design authority and assembly capability.

Threats: Geopolitical supply chain risk, strong competition (Airbus, GS Yuasa, ABSL), and disruptive alternative technologies like solid-state, hydrogen, and nuclear for space.

2. Airbus (Space Division) (France / Europe)⁴⁴

⁴³ <https://saft.com/fr/saft-en-bref>

⁴⁴ <https://www.airbus.com/en/products-services/space/equipment/power/space-battery-products>

Airbus is the largest aeronautics and space company in Europe, providing products, services and solutions for the commercial aviation, helicopter, defence and space sectors. Airbus has developed its own battery products for Space applications since 2016 using COTS Li-ion cells, qualified by Airbus for Space applications and with flight heritage, that enables Airbus to propose a competitive price. Relevant product lines include:

- ASTRO-BATT: product line specifically developed to address Low-Earth Orbit (LEO) missions
- COSMO-BATT: developed for Telecom and Navigation satellites. The design is based on a modular approach in order to cope with specific mission requirements while minimizing the non-recurring costs and battery mass.
- LAUNCHER-BATT modules (launcher units). A dedicated Battery Assembly Line for space.

Strengths: Competitive advantage: proven track records of flight-heritage, qualification, and ability to meet ECSS / EASA / MIL standards. This is a major competitive advantage.

Weaknesses: As a meaningful producer, their environmental impact is more important, which can deteriorate the company image.

Opportunities: Scale & Vertical Integration leveraging in-house design authority and assembly capability.

Threats: Geopolitical supply chain risk, strong competition (Saft, GS Yuasa, ABSL)

3. ABSL Space Products (EnerSys group) (UK / Europe)⁴⁵

Known supplier of Li-ion batteries for space missions. ABSL provides high-reliability battery systems used in spacecraft and satellites. ESA has used ABSL's batteries for missions such as Proba-1 and other smaller satellites.

Strengths: Proven reliability and heritage powered major missions like the James Webb Space Telescope and the Europa Clipper spacecraft. Strong European manufacturing base and certification/quality.

Weaknesses: There's a risk of being outpaced by newer entrants or players pushing more aggressively into high-energy-density, ultra-lightweight, or high-safety alternatives.

Opportunities: Growing demand for satellites, electrification of aviation

Threats: Aerospace/space primes or in-house teams (e.g., satellites built by larger firms with in-house battery integration) may reduce outsourcing. Supply chain and raw material risks depend a lot on third-party suppliers.

4. InoBat (Slovakia / Europe)⁴⁶

A newer player targeting high-performance Li-ion cells for military drones / UAS, aerospace and industrial markets. Their E10 battery cell is specifically designed for unmanned systems, which often require high reliability and performance approaching aerospace-grade standards.

Strengths: Innovation focus - pushing into higher energy, faster charge, or solid-state categories

⁴⁵ <https://www.enersys.com/en/products/batteries/absl/absl-space/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.inobat.eu/>

Weaknesses: Niche and less mature market

Opportunities: Increasing military budgets and public demand in drone technologies.

Threats: High competition with well-established European players investing in research and innovation (Airbus, ABSL, Saft)

5. Solithor + Sonaca (Belgium / Europe)⁴⁷

Partnership to develop solid-state lithium-ion-based battery systems for regional aviation, urban air mobility, and potentially satellites/defense use. Solid-state approaches are especially attractive for safety, energy density, and aerospace performance.

Strengths: Innovation focus - pushing into higher energy, faster charge, or solid-state categories. Collaboration of two European players proposing novel and performant aviation battery solutions.

Weaknesses: Less mature market that is slowly growing.

Opportunities: Increasing R&D for more performant and sustainable battery technologies. Electrification of the aviation industry.

Threats: High competition with well-established European players investing in research and innovation (Airbus, ABSL, Saft)

5.8.3 Key competitors in smart sensors for aviation

It's worth noting that the world's most successful and reliable aviation sensor providers are all based in the United States (US); North America holds the largest market share, accounting for over 40% of the global aerospace sensor market. This impacts especially on the export and safety compliance of the provided solutions. Europe is the second-largest market, with a market share of around 30%. The region is seeing strong growth driven by increasing demand for sensors across both civil and military aviation. Major companies such as Airbus and Rolls-Royce are driving innovations in aerospace sensors, particularly in Europe's space and aviation sectors.

1. PCB Piezotronics (US)⁴⁸

The company is a global leader in sensor technologies, providing high-performance sensors for a variety of applications, including aerospace.

Strengths: Known for their precision and reliability, PCB's sensors are crucial for measuring pressure, vibration, and acceleration in critical aerospace environments.

Weaknesses: Certification requirements from relevant public authorities impose strict qualification (vibration, thermal cycling, radiation) before sensors are accepted in critical systems.

Opportunity: With a strong focus on R&D, PCB Piezotronics ensures that their products meet stringent industry standards while delivering accurate data for flight safety and performance monitoring.

⁴⁷ <https://aviationweek.com/aerospace/advanced-air-mobility/belgium-companies-partner-aircraft-batteries>

⁴⁸ <https://www.pcb.com/>

Threats: Strain/temperature data may be considered safety-critical; storage, transmission, and analytics must meet public data security regulations (US vs. EU).

2. Honeywell Aerospace (US)⁴⁹

Honeywell is a renowned multinational conglomerate that provides cutting-edge aerospace sensor solutions. Their portfolio includes advanced sensors for temperature, pressure, and airflow, all designed to improve system performance and enhance the safety of aerospace applications.

Strengths: Their sensors are integrated into various systems such as aviation engines and flight control, offering critical insights that help in optimizing operational efficiency and safety across commercial and military aviation. Known for their precision and reliability.

Weaknesses: Long qualification cycles and certification cost overruns.

Opportunities: aviation operators prefer turnkey, certified solutions that this renowned company can provide.

Threats: The company is based in the US, and the related export and safety compliance can impact the costs and the delivery delays.

3. TE Connectivity (US)

With AS9100 certified facilities to support Tier 1, 2 and 3 providers, TE Connectivity (TE) delivers a wide variety of critical sensor solutions for aerospace applications. Commercial and military aviation OEMs around the world deploy their solutions. . Together with our customers, we are working to solve today's biggest application challenges in new and creative ways.

Strengths: Their sensors are designed and manufactured to exacting specifications, often on a custom basis.

Weaknesses: Long qualification cycles and certification cost overruns.

Opportunities: Long development cycles and high costs require aerospace companies to identify stable and reliable sensor solutions for which this company is renowned for.

Threats: Company based in the US, and the related export and safety compliance can impact the costs and the delivery delays.

In addition, there are many specialised suppliers and systems integrators. The key aerospace industry actors (such as Airbus) work with these sensor makers or, even more, they develop in-house systems.

5.9 Response to Market Gaps

Where the challenges described in the earlier section focus on the persistent problems of the target market, this part identifies the key gaps where the three target markets have not found sustainable solutions, offering opportunities for novel approaches, such as GRAPHERGIA.

⁴⁹ aerospace.honeywell.com

5.9.1 Gaps in the e-textiles sector

The e-textile market presents several gaps and related opportunities for innovation and development.

- **Integration complexity:** Seamlessly embedding electronic components such as sensors and power sources into textiles remains challenging.⁵⁰
 - This issue requires advancements in materials science and manufacturing techniques to ensure flexibility, comfort, and durability while maintaining the desired electronic functionality⁵¹. GRAPHERGIA creates novel all-in-one self-charging power textiles, integrating several key advancements (processes and components) made in the project in the field of smart textiles. These innovative textiles will seamlessly combine energy harvesting, conversion, and storage functionalities, enabling a battery-free power solution for wearable and IoT-connected applications.
- **Miniaturisation of components:** Gap: Integration of smaller, lighter, and more efficient components (like sensors, batteries, and circuits) is still a challenge.
 - Innovations in nanotechnology and flexible electronics could enable less bulky and more seamless smart textiles. GRAPHERGIA is investigating the potential of TENGs (triboelectric nanogenerators) as e-textile energy-harvesting components.
 - GRAPHERGIA is developing a novel approach to create highly performant micro-flexible supercapacitors integrated into smart textiles.
- **Standardisation and interoperability:** The lack of industry-wide standards for components, communication protocols, and data formats hinders large-scale adoption.
 - Establishing universal standards could simplify integration and foster collaboration across the value chain⁵². GRAPHERGIA is part of the Graphene Flagship collaboration, especially in standardisation efforts and innovation roadmapping of graphene-enabled innovations in energy and beyond.
- **Power and energy management:** Efficient and lightweight energy solutions, such as flexible batteries or energy-harvesting systems, remain underdeveloped. Powering wearable e-textiles for extended periods without adding significant bulk remains a major hurdle.
 - GRAPHERGIA is creating self-powered and IoT-enabled energy-harvesting textiles.
- **Durability and Washability:** The need for e-textiles to endure repeated washing, stretching and physical wear is a critical challenge.
 - Developing textiles with enhanced longevity and robust electronic integration to withstand regular usage and maintenance. GRAPHERGIA is investigating how the self-powered e-textile it created could be used.

⁵⁰ <https://www.technavio.com/report/e-textile-market-industry-analysis> (consulted 18/01/2025)

⁵¹ <https://www.analytica.global/research/e-textile-market> (consulted 28/01/2025)

⁵² www.iom3.org/resource/opportunities-challenges-with-e-textiles-creating-momentum-by-new-standards.html (consulted 28/01/2025)

- **High production costs:** The manufacturing of e-textiles involves specialised materials and complex processes, making them more expensive than conventional textiles. Scaling production while maintaining quality and cost efficiency is a barrier to broader adoption.
 - Exploring cost-effective materials and scalable manufacturing techniques can bridge this gap. GRAPHERGIA aims to optimise an efficient roll-to-roll (R2R) pilot-scale production process.
- **Sustainability concerns:** Environmental challenges, such as the recyclability of components and the sustainability of raw materials, require attention.
 - Developing eco-friendly solutions and reducing waste during production are becoming increasingly crucial as sustainability becomes a key factor in consumer preferences. GRAPHERGIA's novel laser-assisted method for fabricating graphene/Si nanohybrid-based anodes (i) operates under ambient conditions, eliminating high-energy processing steps, (ii) is waste-free and chemical-free, avoiding the environmental footprint of solvent-based conductive inks, and (iii) it uses affordable and renewable carbon sources, reducing material costs.
- **Broad consumer awareness:** Despite growing interest, the average consumer remains unaware of the potential and availability of e-textiles.
 - Effective marketing campaigns and education could boost awareness and drive demand. GRAPHERGIA has an entire work package dedicated to communication and dissemination⁵³, showcasing the key public research activities and results. The aim is to create awareness and provide content that is easily accessible to different stakeholder groups.

5.9.2 Gaps related to Li-ion batteries for space and Aerospace applications

The biggest market gap is that aerospace and space need lighter, safer, and more durable batteries, but Li-ion's evolution is held back by certification lag, high costs, and supply chain fragility.

- **Supply chain dependency and critical materials:** The aerospace-grade lithium battery market is highly vulnerable due to the concentration of supply. Over 75% of global cobalt comes from the DRC, and aerospace requirements demand extremely high-purity lithium; only a handful of refineries can meet this standard. The lack of ethical sources for raw material persists.
 - GRAPHERGIA's innovation includes the approach of Sustainable-by-Design 2D Materials, research managed under work package 5 with the aim to assess the environmental impact of the battery created.
- **Safety and certification set limits for innovation:** Current Li-ion chemistries still face thermal runaway risks – unacceptable in flight or space. There is also a lack of certification frameworks that keep pace with innovation. Moreover, certification for aviation and space

⁵³ <http://graphergia.eu/>

batteries is slow, expensive, and highly restrictive, which delays adoption of new chemistries like solid-state.

- GRAPHERGIA has carried out market research (WP3) and it tailors the custom LIB designs to meet aerospace requirements.
- **Combination of high energy density and low weight:** Not yet sufficient for long-haul aviation or deep space. There is no commercially available Li-ion that meets ultra-high energy density targets without safety compromises.
 - GRAPHERGIA has established a rigorous qualification protocol for our cylindrical cells to guarantee both electrochemical performance and mechanical integrity before CubeSat integration (demo #3).
- **Recycling and end-of-life management:** Recycling infrastructure for aerospace and space batteries is underdeveloped. Recovering high-value materials is still inefficient, especially with unique battery geometries and small volumes. End-of-life batteries—particularly in satellites that burn up or become debris—often result in total material loss.
 - GRAPHERGIA creates an innovative, eco-friendly process for the in-situ, single-step, and binder-free preparation of LIB electrodes based on graphene-related materials, minimizing the need for pre- or post-treatment procedures.

5.9.3 Gaps related to Smart Sensors in Aviation

This market is slowed down by heavy certification processes, sensor integration and weight issues, as well as the lack of standardized modules, underutilized data, and poor ROI clarity.

- **Certification bottlenecks:** Long, expensive qualification processes (DO-160G, ECSS, MIL-STD) delay adoption.
 - GRAPHERGIA pilots the developed structurally Integrated Self-Powered AeroSensor (KER#7) in the demo case #2. This commercial validation will focus on ensuring that the sensor meets requirements for structural integrity, weight, and reliability opening the door for further certification.
- **Integration complexity and weight:** Distributed sensors add cabling, connectors, and interrogators, which increases aviation weight and integration cost. Retrofitting existing fleets is especially challenging due to downtime and wiring costs.
 - GRAPHERGIA develops self-powered, graphene-based wireless sensors that are structurally integrated to the aviation blade structure, which simplifies their integration and allows for lighter weight.
- **Limited wireless and energy-harvesting deployment:** Battery-powered or wired systems dominate but this can add the maintenance burden and add wiring complexity. Wireless sensor networks for aviation are still rare due to complex cybersecurity and certification processes.
- **Data Management and analytics readiness:** High-volume raw data from dense networks (FBG arrays, wireless nodes) is underutilised. The lack of certifiable, explainable AI/analytics frameworks hinders the use of safety-critical decisions.

- **Cost for aviation operators:** To this date, operators remain sceptical of retrofit SHM sensors due to unclear payback periods.

5.10 Opportunities for GRAPHERGIA

The GRAPHERGIA solution, composed of processes, components, and final products, is driven by the growing opportunities in its application areas, including e-textiles, next-gen Li-ion batteries for space, and sensors for aerospace. The GRAPHERGIA system considers these opportunities as part of its exploitation plans, beyond the project duration.

The geopolitical context drives EU and national policies towards greater sovereignty in energy, space, and aerospace applications, increasing not only available budgets but also demand in these sectors. This demand is reinforced by advances in material and technological science, which enable the production of more reliable, sustainable and performant solutions.

5.10.1 Opportunities for GRAPHERGIA: E-textiles

The globally growing e-textile market offers several significant opportunities related to emerging technologies, advances in materials science, increased adoption of sports and health-tracking systems, and growing military and defence sector needs.

- New technologies like the **Internet of Things (IoT) and artificial intelligence (AI) are changing the textile market**. AI can access and gather historical and real-time operational data for health and sports monitoring⁵⁴. Using IoT and Edge Computing reduces the need for batteries and wires through wireless charging and communication technologies. Also, incorporating more sophisticated sensors capable of monitoring a wider range of physiological and environmental parameters.
- Advances in materials science and flexible electronics enable **the use of novel, more performant materials, such as graphene**, notably the smart fabric's monitoring capacity, sensor sizes, and battery performance. Also, enhancing comfort and usability by making electronic components more flexible.
- **Increasing consumer interest in monitoring health and fitness performance** technologies creates opportunities for more durable and functional e-textile products.
- Due to the current geopolitical situation, **growth in military budgets** drives further adoption of e-textiles for military usage.

5.10.2 Opportunities for GRAPHERGIA: Li-ion batteries for space Markets

Electrification of aerospace and the increase of small satellites, as well as improvements in next-gen battery technologies, open opportunities in the Li-ion batteries market in space applications.

⁵⁴<https://www.maximizemarketresearch.com/market-report/global-smart-textile-market/28970/>
(consulted 28/01/2025)

- More missions in space, including the increase in small satellites (such as smallsats or cubesats), increase of commercial space, and earth observation, deep space probes, **drive increasing battery demand, especially for reliable, and long-life batteries.**
- In the current geopolitical context, **European and national space agencies are pushing for sovereign capability** in space technologies, which results in increased budgets for space exploration, defence, climate and satellite monitoring. Moreover, with the **EU space act**⁵⁵, proposed in June 2025, the EC provides a regulatory framework for space activities in the Union with the ambition to create a single market for space activities.
- **Advances in battery technology** create opportunities to integrate newer cell chemistries, improved thermal management, more energy density per mass, and better safety features (radiation, vibration). Also, there is now more potential to reduce costs via modular standardisation, more scalable manufacturing, or co-development with cell manufacturers.

5.10.3 Opportunities for GRAPHERGIA: Smart Sensors for aviation

For GRAPHERGIA's batteryless sensor solution, this target market offers several opportunities, primarily in predictive maintenance of structures, composites & electrification, wireless/energy-harvesting, new space constellations, and pre-certified sensor systems.

- Composite structures in airframes and rotorcraft drive **demand for embedded or distributed strain sensing** (fiber optics, thin-film sensors).
- Electric propulsion, hydrogen fuel cells, and high-density battery packs **require robust temperature sensors for safety and performance.**
- Self-powered wireless sensors **reduce installation complexity and maintenance costs.**
- LEO constellations, cube sats, and small sat platforms **demand miniaturized, radiation-hardened sensors in higher volumes** than traditional space programs.

5.11 GRAPHERGIA's positioning on the markets

5.11.1 GRAPHERGIA addressing challenges and gaps

Smart textiles

- **The production cost:** GRAPHERGIA's novel process of dual-laser application of graphene onto e-textile enables the reduction of the production costs. While traditional printed electrodes require high metal loading (e.g., Ag) to enhance conductivity, GRAPHERGIA's approach eliminates this constraint, enabling a more scalable and cost-effective fabrication of conductive textile-based electrodes.
- **Complex integration of self-harvesting and storage nano-devices:** The simultaneous fabrication and interfacing of TENGs and micro-flexible storage devices, within the same textile, remains as one of the key unsolved issues for developing self-charging power textiles. The challenge arises from the complexity to integrate both devices into the textile and the poor coupling among them due to the substantial capacitance and

⁵⁵ <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/eu-space-programme/> (consulted in October 2025)

impedance mismatch between the harvesting and storage components. GRAPHERGIA's research proposes better autonomy from TENG generators and simple high-voltage management for higher power conversion. As well as , GRAPHERGIA is developing a novel approach to create highly performant micro-flexible supercapacitors integrated to smart textiles.

Li-Ion batteries for aerospace applications

- **Production scalability and cost effectiveness:** GRAPHERGIA develops and pilots the laser deposition process of graphene, allowing for high-throughput, roll-to-roll compatibility, ensuring seamless integration into existing LIB manufacturing lines. This method also reduces electrode processing steps, enhancing production efficiency and cost-effectiveness

Smart sensors for aerospace applications

- **Integration and wiring complexity:** GRAPHERGIA offers a self-powering wireless strain/temperature sensor that integrates with the aviation structure (e.g. wind turbine blades).
- **Harsh environment qualification:** GRAPHERGIA's demo case #2 pilots the sensor in a real-life environment, enabling it to assess its performance and resistance in the real aerospace environment.

GRAPHERGIA targeting specific market needs

Smart textiles

Smart textiles are wearable and connected solutions that enable the monitoring of the users' body signals. Therefore, the solutions must be **flexible, seamless and more importantly, easy to wear and to use**. E-textiles are used especially in healthcare applications, sports performance monitoring, as well as military applications. GRAPHERGIA proposes a novel charge-as-you-go, self-powered smart textile that integrates energy harvesting, conversion, and storage into a seamless, fabric-based solution.

Li-Ion batteries for space and aerospace applications

LIB solutions deployed in space applications (e.g., in-orbit satellites) must be **highly performant, resistant, and comply with strict safety and quality standards**. GRAPHERGIA offers an advanced graphene-based LIB module prototype for space applications (piloted in Cubesats), optimised to deliver high power while maintaining a wide operating temperature window.

Smart sensors for aerospace applications

In general terms, aerospace operators use smart sensors to monitor aviation structural health, engines and propulsion, as well as environmental and thermal controls.

GRAPHERGIA's self-powered sensor solution, integrated into the aviation structure (e.g., blade), measures both temperature and strain. GRAPHERGIA supports the aviation system health management with a batteryless, cost-effective, lightweight and seamless sensor solution.

Moreover, this sensor monitors 1) strain to detect deformation, stress, or potential fatigue in structural components and 2) temperature to identify thermal conditions that may affect material performance.

GRAPHERGIA's competitive advantage

GRAPHERGIA's solution in self-powered energy harvesting and storage is positioned at the nexus of e-textiles, next-generation Li-ion batteries for space, and smart sensors in aerospace. It offers **batteryless, self-charging wearables fabricated with dry electrode technology**, enabling a more sustainable manufacturing process. The competitive advantage over the traditional approach to graphene-enhanced textiles is the laser-based roll-to-roll pilot line, as it eliminates the need for traditional graphene inks and hazardous chemical processing.

Furthermore, the GRAPHERGIA solution is **designed to be sustainable**, thanks to the **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)**, is **incorporated in its creation and development phase** (as part of WP6) to ensure that it deploys the most environmentally sustainable process and resources as possible, especially related to its upstream activities.

GRAPHERGIA's additional value

GRAPHERGIA offers a graphene-enabled **self-powered energy solution** for harvesting and storage. It positions at the forefront of greener material science by implementing laser-driven and eco-design approached generating in 2D material science. By demonstrating the transformation of low-cost polymers and ceramic powders into graphene using dual-laser processing, GRAPHERGIA offers cost reduction and more sustainable methods for the manufacturing of e-textiles and LIB anodes. Moreover, with its **seamless integration** of an energy-powering and harvesting solution, it offers a **lightweight, low-maintenance, and eco-friendly** alternative to conventional power sources. As a first-of-its-kind solution, it paves the way for next-generation, energy-autonomous textiles, sensors and batteries.

Moreover, with a tailored communication and dissemination strategy, GRAPHERGIA continuously **raises public awareness** of the potential of graphene-enabled technologies in energy innovation. It shares its key research **results in open access, enabling stakeholders to** benefit from the gained knowledge and innovation. An active member of the Graphene Flagship ecosystem, GRAPHERGIA collaborates with related projects that are innovating in energy solutions. This way, the project benefits from the exchange of know-how among researchers, business partners and potential customers.

Moreover, GRAPHERGIA brings additional value to the three target markets:

Smart textiles

- **Roll-2-roll pilot line:** Our novel laser-based R2R pilot line revolutionises the fabrication of graphene-enhanced textiles, paving the way for the next generation of smart clothing and wearable electronics. By eliminating the need for traditional graphene inks and hazardous chemical processing, our direct laser-assisted deposition process ensures a scalable, cost-

effective, and environmentally sustainable method for integrating conductive graphene structures into fabrics.

- **Self-powering smart textile:** By integrating triboelectric charge collection directly into the textile substrate, our process enables next-generation smart textiles and wearable electronics with built-in energy harvesting capabilities—meeting the growing demand for sustainable, self-powered devices in various applications.

Li-Ion batteries for space and aerospace applications

GRAPHERGIA's novel laser-assisted method for fabricating graphene/Si nanohybrid-based anodes delivers a disruptive, scalable, and eco-friendly solution for manufacturing highly performant next-generation lithium-ion batteries.

- **Binder-free, solvent-free, and sustainable process:** This eliminates the need for polymeric binders and toxic NMP solvents, reducing manufacturing costs and environmental impact. It also supports circular economy principles by enabling waste-free processing at ambient conditions.
- **Scalability and industrial integration:** Direct laser deposition allows for high-throughput, roll-to-roll compatibility, ensuring seamless integration into existing LIB manufacturing lines. This method also reduces electrode processing steps, enhancing production efficiency and cost-effectiveness.
- **Faster charging capability:** Laser-created microchannels and trenches accelerate electrolyte diffusion, enabling faster charge/discharge rates for high-power applications. Optimised electrode porosity enhances Li-ion transport, minimising capacity fade at high currents.

Smart sensors for space & aerospace applications

- **Self-powered and integrated sensor:** The novel self-powered, structurally integrated sensor offers continuous, real-time monitoring of material state in aerospace and wind turbine structures, enhancing safety, reliability, and operational efficiency.
- **Lightweight and wireless solution:** By eliminating the need for batteries and integrating seamlessly into CFRP blades, it provides a lightweight, wireless solution that ensures long-term, maintenance-free performance in critical environments.

5.12 GRAPHERGIA's SWOT Analysis

The SWOT analysis is a valuable tool for understanding the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with a project or organisation. By conducting a SWOT analysis, GRAPHERGIA can gain a comprehensive understanding of its current market position and identify strategies to maximise its impact and achieve its goals. This analysis will help the project team leverage its strengths, address its weaknesses, capitalise on opportunities, and mitigate threats.

Table 23: GRAPHERGIA's SWOT Analysis

GRAPHERGIA's SWOT Analysis	
<p>STRENGTHS</p> <p>Seamless and integrated power solution: integrated into the smart fabrics or structures with lightweight.</p> <p>Roll-to-roll laser deposition of graphene: scalable, cost efficient and sustainable method.</p> <p>Self-charging: able to harvest and store energy with the TENG.</p> <p>High-capacity LIB anodes: tailored for space applications.</p>	<p>WEAKNESSES</p> <p>Safety and regulation compliance: strict and long processes when dealing with health monitoring, space and aerospace application.</p> <p>Strong competition with well-established industrial players; especially in space and aerospace sectors (Airbus, Boeing, Rolls Royce, etc.) offer both sensor and battery technologies.</p>

Penal

OPPORTUNITIES

Cost-effective: Scalable laser-assisted graphene deposition enables reducing production costs.

Nanostructures: The innovation in TENGs and micro-flexible supercapacitors enables small, lightweight integration into energy-harvesting and storage applications.

Sustainable: GRAPHERGIA offers processes that reduce the use of CRM and wet chemistry, resulting in a greener manufacturing footprint. It is created with the LCA.

Collaboration with established players: GRAPHERGIA's power solution can be integrated in already operating environments (e.g., aviation structures, satellites).

THREATS

Dependence on geopolitical context: raw materials are provided by regions where labour rights and environmental rights are at threat.

Dependence on public authorities: the major part of available funding depends on the public policies (in R&D, military/defence, sovereignty)

Rapid technological advancements: May struggle to keep pace, requiring ongoing development and updates to remain competitive.

Evolving safety and data protection regulations: Changes in these regulations may affect the use of the framework, requiring businesses to adapt their practices accordingly.

Pending for E

6 NEXT STEPS

The GRAPHERGIA project has progressed according to the impact strategy, achieving very good results, notably in terms of visibility, stakeholder event engagement, and the definition of key innovation outcomes. During the second phase (from M26 onwards) and towards the end of the project, the pace of the impact management, covering the community building, communication, dissemination, exploitation and IPR management, will only increase as the project achieves more tangible scientific results.

Community building will continue across the two key pillars, including the GRAPHERGIA hub, where more webinars and joint sessions will be organised, focusing on topics of interest to partners and collaborators. The aim is to have 100+ active members in the GRAPHERGIA hub who are invited not only to participate but also to contribute to the community, for example, by completing online surveys that provide feedback on crucial topics such as innovation management and validation. GRAPHERGIA continues to collaborate with the Graphene Flagship initiative and its sister projects, especially in planning contributions to Graphene Week 2026 and new joint communication and dissemination actions.

In terms of Communication, the planned actions and objectives are progressing smoothly; therefore, the initiated strategy and actions will be followed up. The project continues to promote its scientific results and the researchers behind them. And to complement these topics, it will also create more content dedicated to use cases and the exploitation of the results. Furthermore, the podcast series will be released in January 2026.

In terms of Dissemination, the project continues its successful efforts to share its research at stakeholder events, including scientific conferences and relevant third-party events. Also, GRAPHERGIA will join Graphene Week 2026 in Porto next September. More results will be published in open access, especially new scientific publications in journals and conferences.

Regarding Exploitation, this forthcoming phase will be crucial to the entire consortium and the innovation management to be foreseen beyond the project duration. In the coming months, the partners will carry out dedicated key exploitation results task forces enabling further refinement of the partners' joint/individual exploitation plans, to work on the business models and to carry out the IPR management actions, especially related to filing the potential resulting patents, as well as to start establishing the licensing agreements. In these actions, the support of EUGL and their EU patent attorney will be essential to the partnership.

ANNEX 1- LIST OF COLLABORATIONS WITH SISTER PROJECTS

Month (Year)	Activity type	Collaborators	Description	Impact
Ongoing	Podcast	ARMS, MUNASET, 2D-Biopad and Graphene Flagship	Podcast recording at Graphene Week 2025. GRAPHERGIA worked with GF i to record two podcast episodes. One focused on sustainability and future energy, meanwhile, the other on biosensors and biomedicine, featuring some of its own scientists and innovators.	<p>The Humanside of Graphene Podcast series was produced as part of the GRAPHERGIA project and aims to showcase the larger societal impact of graphene-enabled products. The two episodes were recorded with support from GF i and with speakers from three sister projects.</p> <p>1. Episode on biosensing involved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maria Abrahamsson (Graphene Flagship's Director) - Host - Nasos Masouras (Pleione Energy - GRAPHERGIA) - Hamed Pourkheirollah (Tampere University - ARMS) - Jinhua Sun (Chalmers University of Technology - ARMS) <p>2: Episode on future energy solutions involved</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Amaia Zurutuza (Graphenea) - Host - Spyros Tsiotos (Adamant Composites - GRAPHERGIA) - Alexey Tarasov (MUNASET) - Vincent Bouchiat (Grapheal - 2D-BioPAD)
September 2025	Workshop	GIANCE	The GIANCE Workshop Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), focused on sustainability and environmental assessment of graphene applications, gave GRAPHERGIA the opportunity to discuss life-cycle analysis and sustainability metrics. . Hosted on Graphene Week 2025 on September 2'th, 2025.	This workshop gathered around 30 participants and included four keynote presentations. GRAPHERGIA was able to connect with the relevant research initiatives in the LCA. Matteo Maccanti, Environmental Researcher and LCA Analyst at Next Technology Tecnotessile (NTT) from the GRAPHERGIA project contributed to the workshop's core debate, moderated by Ana Claudia Nioac de Salles, from Fraunhofer ICT, and joined by other key voices from the field: Johan Ek Weis (Chalmers Industriteknik, SIO Grafen), Susanna Andreasi Bassi (JRC European Platform on LCA), and Antonio Valente (ecoinvent).
September 2025	Workshop	SAFARI	Co-organised workshop between GRAPHERGIA and SAFARI, titled "Safe and Sustainable-by-Design 2D Materials for Energy, Electronics, and Biotechnology". Hosted on Graphene Week 2025 on September 25th, 2025.	<p>The session, chaired by Diana Marcano (Poznań Institute of Technology), with Nadia Bali, Postdoctoral Researcher at ICEHT/FORTH, and Matteo Maccanti (NTT) as the GRAPHERGIA speakers, emphasised safe, scalable, and environmentally conscious approaches to next-generation 2D materials.</p> <p>Nadia and Matteo were joined by Kyle Matthews, the workshop's guest speaker, Co-Founder and CTO at MXene Inc., a spin-off from</p>

				Drexel University, built on a foundation of cutting-edge research and innovation to commercialize and scale MXene technology in the United States, and João Laranjeira, Project Manager and Researcher at ISQ, who spoke about the safe and sustainable-by-design approach for 2D materials in the SAFARI project.
Ongoing	Technical collaboration	ARMS	Collaboration in research: exchange of samples.	Technical collaboration: FORTH prepared and shipped material to Tampere Univeristy
Ongoing	Technical collaboration	2D-Printable	Collaboration in research: exchange of samples.	Technical collaboration: FORTH prepared and shipped porous graphene electrodes to Trinity College team at 2D-Printable for characterization using the advanced techniques available in their laboratory.
May 2025	Workshop	2D-Printable	Collaboration at 9th Graphene Flagship EU-Korea international workshop on graphene and 2D materials. This event was organized in May 2025, in Strassbourg (France). In the context of the consolidated collaboration between the Graphene Flagship and the Korean Graphene Society, and the workshop was co-organized by both institutions. Paolo Samori, coordinator of the 2D-PRINTABLE project, chaired this workshop, joined by 15 participants coming from ARMS, GIANCE, 2D-PL, 2DNeuralVision, and GRAPHERGIA.	Our coordinator Spyros Yannopoulos from FORTH was a guest speaker, with his talk entitled: "Laser-assisted production of high-quality graphene and graphene-based nanohybrids: Innovative processes in energy storage devices".
May 2025	Online article	2D-BIOPAD, GRAPHERGIA, MUNASET, SAFARI	Joint article focused on biosensing with graphene-enabled tools. Title: "Graphene Flagship - 2D Materials Innovation for Biomedical Applications".	Joint dissemination activity focusing on awareness publications. This publication was released on the GFI website and all involved project's websites enabling us to reach out to even more target audiences.
February 2025	Online article	Graphene Flagship, GRAPHERGIA, ARMS	Joint online article " Graphene energy storage for a sustainable future" on Innovation News Network	A joint online article was released on an external online media platform on 12.02.2025. This publication on a well-established online platform enabled us to reach out to even more target audiences.
January 2025	Webinar	GRAPHERGIA, 2D-BioPAD, ARMS, GIANCE and 2D-PRINTABLE	GRAPHERGIA proposed a webinar about European patents and IPR management in EU project.	32 participants across the projects. This session enabled capacity building across sister projects.
September 2024	Workshop	EMPHASIS and INERRANT	A satellite event of the 15th International Conference on Solid State Chemistry (SSC 2024),took place from September 8 to 13, 2024, in Ústí nad Labem, Czech Republic, as part of SSC2024. Three sister projects hosted a joint	This event gathered around 40 researchers and experts from diverse backgrounds to discuss the latest advances in electrochemical energy storage, with a particular emphasis on supercapacitors and batteries. It offered an arena for discussions and facilitate knowledge sharing in this rapidly evolving field. It will also offered networking

			workshop focusing on “Electrochemical Energy Storage Materials and Processes”.	opportunities for participants to connect with peers, exchange ideas, and explore potential collaborations.
June & September 2024	Workshop	ARMS	Organisation of two joint workshops in 2024. 1. GRAPHERGIA joins the ARMS project workshop hosted at IEEE FLEPS Seminar in Finland 30th of June 2024. 2. At Graphene Week 2024 a co-hosted workshop entitled "Integrating Graphene Innovations: From Smart Textiles to High-Performance Energy Storage"	In total, these two co-hosted workshops enabled the projects to reach out to over 170 stakeholders.
Continuous	Synergy	Battery 2030	FORTH represents GRAPHERGIA within this initiative to find synergies with projects dealing with the same research topics.	This activity will be fed to the GRAPHERGIA Hub, a collaboration platform connecting researchers in graphene, smart textiles and batteries.

Pending for EC approval

ANNEX 2 – LIST OF THE FEATURED EXTERNAL NEWSLETTERS

Date	Title	Publisher	Link
13/11/2025	The AUSTRALO Perspective: Shaping Impact Through Communication	AUSTRALO	Link
6/11/2025	Graphene Flagship Quarterly Newsletter - November 2025	Graphene Flagship	<i>Available only to the subscribed members</i>
14/10/2025	Check out the Latest Opportunities in Industry 5.0, Deep Tech & Fast-Track Innovation Projects where AUSTRALO is driving Impact through Communication!	AUSTRALO	Link
09/09/2025	Check out the Latest Opportunities in Industry 5.0, Deep Tech & Fast-Track Innovation Projects where AUSTRALO is driving Impact through Communication!	AUSTRALO	Link
12/08/2025	Check out the Latest Opportunities in Industry 5.0 & Deep Tech Projects! And look at what AUSTRALO has done in the past month.	AUSTRALO	Link
08/07/2025	Check out the Latest Opportunities in Industry 5.0 & Deep Tech Projects! And look at what AUSTRALO has done in the past month.	AUSTRALO	Link
17/06/2025	Check out the Latest Opportunities in Industry 5.0 & Deep Tech Projects! And look at what AUSTRALO has done in the past month.	AUSTRALO	Link
02/06/2025	Graphene Flagship Quarterly Newsletter - May 2025	Graphene Flagship	<i>Available only to the subscribed members</i>
13/05/2025	Check out the Latest Opportunities in Industry 5.0 & Deep Tech Projects! And look at what AUSTRALO has done in the past month.	AUSTRALO	Link
08/04/2025	Latest Opportunities in Industry 5.0, Fast-Track Innovation & Deep Tech!	AUSTRALO	Link
11/03/2025	Follow us on our journey through leading communication for European projects!	AUSTRALO	Link
03/03/2025	Graphene Flagship Quarterly Newsletter - February 2025	Graphene Flagship	<i>Available only to the subscribed members</i>
11/02/2025	Follow us on our journey through leading communication for European projects!	AUSTRALO	Link
14/01/2025	Follow us on our journey through leading communication for European projects!	AUSTRALO	Link
10/12/2024	Follow us on our journey through leading communication for European projects!	AUSTRALO	Link
28/11/2024	Project ARMS newsletter #2 (November 2024)	ARMS Project	Link
20/11/2024	Graphene Flagship Quarterly Newsletter - November 2024	Graphene Flagship	<i>Available only to the subscribed members</i>

12/11/2024	Follow us on our journey through leading communication for European projects!	AUSTRALO	Link
08/10/2024	Follow us on our journey through leading communication for those European projects!	AUSTRALO	Link
10/09/2024	Follow us on our journey through leading communication for those European projects!	AUSTRALO	Link
13/08/2024	Follow us on our journey through leading communication for those European projects!	AUSTRALO	Link
09/07/2024	The latest AUSTRALO newsletter is out!	AUSTRALO	Link
11/06/2024	The latest AUSTRALO newsletter is out!	AUSTRALO	Link
07/05/2024	The latest AUSTRALO newsletter is out!	AUSTRALO	Link
16/04/2024	Graphene Flagship Quarterly Newsletter - April 2024	GFi	<i>Available only to the subscribed members</i>
09/04/2024	The latest AUSTRALO newsletter is out!	AUSTRALO	Link
19/03/2024	The latest AUSTRALO newsletter is out!	AUSTRALO	Link
13/02/2024	Unveiling the team behind the #GRAPHERGIAproject!	AUSTRALO	Link
09/01/2024	Learn more about the GRAPHERGIA Project to revolutionize energy harvesting in textiles and battery technology	AUSTRALO	Link
14/11/2023	The Graphene-Info newsletter (November 14, 2023)	Graphene-Info	Link

Pending for EU

ANNEX 3 – LIST OF ALL GRAPHERGIA BLOG POSTS

This table lists the 70 GRAPHERGIA blog posts, ordered from most recent to oldest, that have gathered over 4.000 views from December 2023 to October 2025. The bolded lines highlight the most viewed posts.

Date	Title	Category	Link	Views
29/10/2025	GRAPHERGIA Newsflash #4 - October 2025: Advancing Sustainable Energy Solutions Across Europe	Newsletter	https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/29/graphergia-newsflash-4-october-2025-advancing-sustainable-energy-solutions-across-europe/	19
28/10/2025	GRAPHERGIA at the 248th ECS Meeting: Exploring Graphene's Potential in Electrochemical Energy Storage	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/28/graphergia-at-the-248th-ecs-meeting-exploring-graphenes-potential-in-electrochemical-energy-storage/	28
23/10/2025	GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinar Series: Join our Session on Laser-Induced Graphene and MXenes for Wearable Devices	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/23/graphergia-hub-webinar-series-join-our-session-on-laser-induced-graphene-and-mxenes-for-wearable-devices/	40
16/10/2025	Inside the GRAPHERGIA Lab: Interviews with our Early-Career Researchers - Meet Sangha Mitra	Interview	https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/16/inside-the-graphergia-lab-interviews-with-our-early-career-researchers-sangha-mitra/	48
09/10/2025	GRAPHERGIA Year 2: From Lab to Fabric - Advancing Sustainable Energy Solutions Across Europe	Article & News	https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/09/graphergia-year-2-from-lab-to-fabric-advancing-sustainable-energy-solutions-across-europe/	68
09/10/2025	GRAPHERGIA Abstract: Ionic Liquid Integrated High-Voltage Polymer Gel Electrolyte to Improve the Capacitance and Cyclic Stability of Supercapacitors	Scientific Publication	https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/06/graphergia-abstract-ionic-liquid-integrated-high-voltage-polymer-gel-electrolyte-to-improve-the-capacitance-and-cyclic-stability-of-supercapacitors/	17
02/10/2025	GRAPHERGIA at Graphene Week 2025: A Chronicle of Energy, Innovation, Sustainability, and Connections	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2025/10/02/graphergia-at-graphene-week-2025-a-chronicle-of-energy-innovation-sustainability-and-connections/	45
12/09/2025	GRAPHERGIA at ISE20: Exploring the Future of Textile Tribo-Electrets for Energy Harvesting	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2025/09/12/graphergia-at-ise20-exploring-the-future-of-textile-tribo-electrets-for-energy-harvesting/	19

10/09/2025	GRAPHERGIA at mESC-IS 2025: Pioneering Graphene Innovation in Energy Storage and Conversion	Event		https://graphergia.eu/2025/09/10/graphergia-at-mesc-is-2025-pioneering-graphene-innovation-in-energy-storage-and-conversion/	35
26/08/2025	Energy Meets Innovation: The GRAPHERGIA Project Activities at Graphene Week 2025 in Vicenza	Event		https://graphergia.eu/2025/08/26/energy-meets-innovation-the-graphergia-project-activities-at-graphene-week-2025-in-vicenza/	134
08/07/2025	2D Materials Innovation for Biomedical Applications - A Joint Article by 2D-BioPAD, MUNASET, SAFARI and GRAPHERGIA	Article News	&	https://graphergia.eu/2025/07/08/2d-materials-innovation-for-biomedical-applications-a-joint-article-by-2d-biopad-munaset-safari-and-graphergia/	24
18/06/2025	GRAPHERGIA at the Graphene Flagship Annual Report 2024: Highlights, Dissemination and Exploitation	Article News	&	https://graphergia.eu/2025/06/18/graphergia-at-the-graphene-flagship-annual-report-2024-highlights-dissemination-and-exploitation/	45
10/06/2025	GRAPHERGIA Introduces Students to Modern Scientific Instrumentation through School Visits	Article News	&	https://graphergia.eu/2025/06/10/graphergia-introduces-students-to-modern-scientific-instrumentation-through-school-visits/	24
09/06/2025	GRAPHERGIA's May 2025 Events Calendar: Spreading our Graphene and 2D Materials Research all over the World	Event		https://graphergia.eu/2025/06/09/graphergias-may-2025-event-calendar-spreading-our-research-all-over-the-world/	70
02/06/2025	GRAPHERGIA Abstract: Polymer Electrolyte Based Flexible Micro-Supercapacitors for Future Aerospace and Smart e-Textile Applications	Scientific Publication		https://graphergia.eu/2025/06/02/graphergia-abstract-polymer-electrolyte-based-flexible-micro-supercapacitors-for-future-aerospace-and-smart-e-textile-applications/	25
26/05/2025	GRAPHERGIA Spreads our Project Research Activities in the International Scientific Community Boosting Energy Innovation	Article News	&	https://graphergia.eu/2025/05/26/graphergia-expands-our-project-research-activities-in-the-international-scientific-community-boosting-energy-innovation/	46
21/05/2025	The GRAPHERGIA Partners Meet in Paris to Prepare the Activities for the Second Half of the Project	Article News	&	https://graphergia.eu/2025/05/21/the-graphergia-partners-meet-in-paris-to-prepare-the-activities-for-the-second-half-of-the-project/	42
15/05/2025	GRAPHERGIA Scientific Publication: Solving ZIB challenges: the dynamic role of water in deep eutectic solvents electrolyte	Scientific Publication		https://graphergia.eu/2025/05/15/graphergia-scientific-publication-solving-zib-challenges-the-dynamic-role-of-water-in-deep-eutectic-solvents-electrolyte/	20

15/05/2025	GRAPHERGIA Scientific Publication: Temperature Dependence of Coherent versus Spontaneous Raman Scattering	Scientific Publication	https://graphergia.eu/2025/05/15/graphergia-scientific-publication-temperature-dependence-of-coherent-versus-spontaneous-raman-scattering/	19
15/05/2025	GRAPHERGIA Abstract: Quasi-solid polymer electrolytes for all-in-one self-charging structural energy storage devices	Scientific Publication	https://graphergia.eu/2025/05/15/graphergia-abstract-quasi-solid-polymer-electrolytes-for-all-in-one-self-charging-structural-energy-storage-devices/	32
15/05/2025	GRAPHERGIA Abstract: Fabrication of Laser-Induced Micro-Supercapacitors for Structurally-Integrated Power Storage Systems	Scientific Publication	https://graphergia.eu/2025/05/15/graphergia-abstract-fabrication-of-laser-induced-micro-supercapacitors-for-structurally-integrated-power-storage-systems/	25
03/04/2025	GRAPHERGIA Newsflash #3 - April 2025: Sustainability Assessment & Eco-Design for Graphene-Based Products	Newsletter	https://graphergia.eu/2025/04/03/graphergia-newsflash-3-april-2025-sustainability-assessment-eco-design-for-graphene-based-products/	23
31/03/2025	GRAPHERGIA Partners Speak about Sustainability Assessment & Eco-Design for Graphene-Based Products in the Second GRAPHERGIA Hub Webinar Series	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2025/03/31/graphergia-partners-speak-about-sustainability-assessment-eco-design-for-graphene-based-products-in-the-second-graphergia-hub-webinar-series/	79
17/03/2025	GRAPHERGIA Hub Invites you to our Webinar on Sustainability Assessment & Eco-Design for Graphene-Based Products	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2025/03/17/graphergia-hub-invites-you-to-their-webinar-on-sustainability-assessment-eco-design-for-graphene-based-products/	97
07/03/2025	GRAPHERGIA Scientific Publication: X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy Analysis of Electrospun Polyacrylonitrile Fibers	Scientific Publication	https://graphergia.eu/2025/03/07/graphergia-scientific-publication-x-ray-photoelectron-spectroscopy-analysis-of-electrospun-polyacrylonitrile-fibers/	39
03/03/2025	GRAPHERGIA Scientific Publication: Power Management Technologies for Triboelectric Nanogenerators	Scientific Publication	https://graphergia.eu/2025/03/03/graphergia-scientific-publication-power-management-technologies-for-triboelectric-nanogenerators/	45
27/02/2025	GRAPHERGIA Presents at Large-area, Organic & Printed Electronics Convention (LOPEC) 2025	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2025/02/27/graphergia-presented-at-large-area-organic-printed-electronics-convention-lopec-2025/	26
14/02/2025	GRAPHERGIA Scientific Publication: Dry Laser-Assisted Fabrication of F-doped Graphene Electrodes: Boosting the Performance of Zn-ion Hybrid Capacitors	Scientific Publication	https://graphergia.eu/2025/02/14/graphergia-scientific-publication-dry-laser-assisted-fabrication-of-f-doped-graphene-electrodes-boosting-the-performance-of-zn-ion-hybrid-capacitors/	55

30/01/2025	GRAPHERGIA Hub Presents our First Webinar Dedicated to IPR Management	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2025/01/30/graphergia-hub-presents-our-first-webinar-dedicated-to-ipr-management/	112
28/01/2025	GRAPHERGIA Scientific Publication: On The Optimal Choice Of Electrical Conditioning Circuits For Triboelectric Nanogenerators	Scientific Publication	https://graphergia.eu/2025/01/28/scientific-publication-on-the-optimal-choice-of-electrical-conditioning-circuits-for-triboelectric-nanogenerators/	45
04/12/2024	GRAPHERGIA Poster: Innovative Pilot Lines for Sustainable Graphene-based Flexible & Structural Energy Harvesting & Storage Devices	Scientific Publication	https://graphergia.eu/2024/12/04/graphergia-poster-innovative-pilot-lines-for-sustainable-graphene-based-flexible-structural-energy-harvesting-storage-devices/	47
04/12/2024	GRAPHERGIA Poster: Smart Textiles based on Triboelectric Nanogenerators	Scientific Publication	https://graphergia.eu/2024/12/04/graphergia-poster-smart-textiles-based-on-triboelectric-nanogenerators/	42
03/12/2024	GRAPHERGIA Presents its First Scientific Paper at PowerMEMS+ 2024	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/12/03/graphergia-presents-its-first-scientific-paper-at-powermems-2024/	66
07/11/2024	GRAPHERGIA Newsflash #2 - November 2024: Towards an Innovative Energy Landscape with Graphene for a Climate-Neutral Future	Newsletter	https://graphergia.eu/2024/11/07/graphergia-newsflash-2-november-2024-towards-an-innovative-energy-landscape-with-graphene-for-a-climate-neutral-future/	29
06/11/2024	Unveiling the Team behind the GRAPHERGIA Project - Meet AUSTRALO Marketing Lab	Interview	https://graphergia.eu/2024/11/06/unveiling-the-team-behind-the-graphergia-project-meet-australo-marketing-lab/	67
31/10/2024	GRAPHERGIA at the Graphene Week 2024: A Strong GrapheneEU Projects Community Is Key for our Common Good	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/10/31/graphergia-at-the-graphene-week-2024-a-strong-grapheneeu-projects-community-is-key-for-our-common-good/	121
25/10/2024	The GRAPHERGIA Team Gathers in the Italian City of Prato for the 2nd Consortium Meeting to Reflect on the Year 1 Achievements	Article & News	https://graphergia.eu/2024/10/25/the-graphergia-team-gathers-in-the-italian-city-of-prato-for-the-2nd-consortium-meeting-to-reflect-on-the-year-1-achievements/	33
24/10/2024	GRAPHERGIA Joins the Micro-and Nano Engineering (MNE) 2024 Conference with a Presentation about Supercapacitors for Power Storage	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/10/24/graphergia-joins-the-micro-and-nano-engineering-mne-2024-conference-with-a-presentation-about-supercapacitors-for-power-storage/	40
10/10/2024	GRAPHERGIA Co-Organises a Workshop about Smart Textiles and Energy Storage with the ARMS Project at the Graphene Week 2024	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/10/10/our-workshop-agenda-integrating-graphene-innovations-from-smart-textiles-to-high-performance-energy-storage/	74

03/10/2024	GRAPHERGIA Year 1: Revolutionizing our Energy Harvesting and Storage Landscape with Graphene for a Climate-Neutral Future	Article News &	https://graphergia.eu/2024/10/03/graphergia-year-1-revolutionizing-our-energy-harvesting-and-storage-landscape-with-graphene-for-a-climate-neutral-future/	55
02/10/2024	A Master Student from FORTH Speaks about her GRAPHERGIA Research at the XXXVIII Panhellenic Conference on Solid State Physics and Materials Science	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/10/02/a-phd-student-from-forth-speaks-about-her-graphergia-research-at-the-xxxviii-panhellenic-conference-on-solid-state-physics-and-materials-science/	79
29/09/2024	Our Partner Université Gustave Eiffel Participates in a Symposium at the Materials Challenges in Alternative and Renewable Energy 2024 Conference	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/09/29/our-partner-universite-gustave-eiffel-participates-in-the-materials-challenges-in-alternative-and-renewable-energy-2024-conference-with-a-symposium/	49
26/09/2024	The GRAPHERGIA partner "Sapienza" University of Rome Hosts the 28th International Conference on Raman Spectroscopy	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/09/26/the-graphergia-partner-sapienza-university-of-rome-hosts-the-28th-international-conference-on-raman-spectroscopy/	46
22/09/2024	GRAPHERGIA Co-hosts the Horizon Europe Satellite Event at the 15th International Conference on Solid State Chemistry 2024 with the EMPHASIS and INERRANT Projects	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/09/22/graphergia-co-hosts-the-horizon-europe-satellite-event-at-the-15th-international-conference-on-solid-state-chemistry-2024-with-the-emphasis-and-inerrant-projects/	79
12/09/2024	The GRAPHERGIA Project Participates in the Graphene Week 2024 with a Workshop and Two Posters Presentations	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/09/12/the-graphergia-project-participates-in-the-graphene-week-2024-with-a-workshop-and-two-posters-presentations/	117
22/08/2024	Unveiling the Team behind the GRAPHERGIA Project - Meet Sapienza University of Rome	Interview	https://graphergia.eu/2024/08/22/unveiling-the-team-behind-the-graphergia-project-meet-sapienza-university-of-rome/	88
31/07/2024	What is GRAPHERGIA? The EU-funded Project Powering Future Energy with Graphene	Article News &	https://graphergia.eu/2024/07/31/what-is-graphergia-the-eu-funded-project-powering-future-energy-with-graphene/	78
30/07/2024	GRAPHERGIA Participates in a Workshop about Synergizing Sustainability in the IEEE FLEPS 2024 Conference in Tampere	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/07/30/graphergia-participates-in-a-workshop-about-synergizing-sustainability-in-the-ieee-fleps-2024-conference-in-tampere/	59
23/07/2024	Unveiling the Team behind the GRAPHERGIA Project - Meet Université Gustave Eiffel	Interview	https://graphergia.eu/2024/07/23/unveiling-the-team-behind-the-graphergia-project-meet-universite-gustave-eiffel/	94

12/07/2024	GRAPHERGIA Participates at the ICOOPMA 2024 Conference with an Invited Talk about Laser Sources to Produce High-Quality Graphene	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/07/01/graphergia-participates-at-the-icoopma-2024-conference-with-an-invited-talk-about-laser-sources-to-produce-high-quality-graphene/	59
27/06/2024	Unveiling the Team behind the GRAPHERGIA Project - Meet German Aerospace Center (DLR)	Interview	https://graphergia.eu/2024/06/27/unveiling-the-team-behind-the-graphergia-project-meet-german-aerospace-center-dlr/	105
25/06/2024	A GRAPHERGIA Partner Co-hosts a Symposium on Nanogenerators at the European Materials Research Society 2024 Spring Meeting	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/06/25/a-graphergia-partner-co-hosts-a-symposium-on-nanogenerators-at-the-european-materials-research-society-2024-spring-meeting/	53
13/06/2024	The Graphene Flagship Annual Report 2023 Features the GRAPHERGIA Project	Article & News	https://graphergia.eu/2024/06/13/the-graphene-flagship-annual-report-2023-features-the-graphergia-project/	53
28/05/2024	How does the GRAPHERGIA Project Work?	Article & News	https://graphergia.eu/2024/05/28/how-does-the-graphergia-project-work/	111
23/05/2024	Unveiling the Team behind the GRAPHERGIA Project - Meet Born Knitting Engineers	Interview	https://graphergia.eu/2024/05/23/unveiling-the-team-behind-the-graphergia-project-meet-born-knitting-engineers/	64
15/05/2024	Unveiling the Team behind the GRAPHERGIA Project - Meet Next Technology Tecnotessile	Interview	https://graphergia.eu/2024/05/15/unveiling-the-team-behind-the-graphergia-project-meet-next-technology-tecnotessile/	90
30/04/2024	Deliverable 1.2 Data Management Plan	Deliverable	https://graphergia.eu/2024/04/30/deliverable-1-2-data-management-plan/	32
18/04/2024	AUSTRALO Hosts the First GRAPHERGIA Exploitation Workshop for the GRAPHERGIA Project Partners	Article & News	https://graphergia.eu/2024/04/18/australo-hosts-the-first-graphergia-exploitation-workshop-for-the-graphergia-project-partners/	32
15/04/2024	GRAPHERGIA Roll-up: Powering the Future with Graphene	Article & News	https://graphergia.eu/2024/04/15/graphergia-roll-up-powering-the-future-with-graphene/	19
26/03/2024	GRAPHERGIA Newsflash #1 - March 2024: Revolutionizing Energy Harvesting in Textiles and Battery Technology	Newsletter	https://graphergia.eu/2024/03/26/graphergia-newsflash-1-march-2024-revolutionizing-energy-harvesting-in-textiles-and-battery-technology/	26
25/03/2024	Deliverable 7.1 Plan for the Dissemination, and Exploitation and Communication of Results - First Version	Deliverable	https://graphergia.eu/2024/03/25/deliverable-7-1-plan-for-the-dissemination-and-exploitation-and-communication-of-results-first-version/	61
13/03/2024	Unveiling the Team behind the GRAPHERGIA Project - Meet Adamant Composites	Interview	https://graphergia.eu/2024/03/13/unveiling-the-team-behind-the-graphergia-project-meet-adamant-composites/	132

01/03/2024	GRAPHERGIA Flyer: Innovative Pilot Lines for Sustainable Graphene-based Flexible & Structural Energy Harvesting & Storage Devices	Article & News	https://graphergia.eu/2024/03/01/graphergia-flyer-innovative-pilot-lines-for-sustainable-graphene-based-flexible-structural-energy-harvesting-storage-devices/	51
20/02/2024	Unveiling the team behind the GRAPHERGIA project - Meet Pleione Energy	Interview	https://graphergia.eu/2024/02/20/unveiling-the-team-behind-the-graphergia-project-meet-pleione-energy/	98
06/02/2024	Joint Kick-Off Meeting With The Graphene Flagship Sister Projects - Establishing Contacts And Opportunities For Synergies	Event	https://graphergia.eu/2024/02/06/joint-kick-off-meeting-with-the-graphene-flagship-sister-projects-establishing-contacts-and-opportunities-for-synergies/	82
31/01/2024	Unveiling the team behind the GRAPHERGIA Project - Meet FORTH: FOUNDATION FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY - HELLAS	Interview	https://graphergia.eu/2024/01/31/unveiling-the-team-behind-the-graphergia-project-meet-forth-foundation-for-research-and-technology-hellas/	227
25/01/2024	Why is the GRAPHERGIA project part of the Graphene Flagship initiative?	Article & News	https://graphergia.eu/2024/01/25/why-is-the-graphergia-project-part-of-the-graphene-flagship-initiative/	68
09/01/2024	Deliverable 1.1 Project Management Plan	Deliverable	https://graphergia.eu/2024/01/09/deliverable-1-1-project-management-plan/	68
09/11/2023	GRAPHERGIA Kick-Off Meeting Hosted in Patras, Greece	Article & News	https://graphergia.eu/2023/11/09/graphergia-kick-off-meeting-hosted-in-patras-greece/	77
06/11/2023	European Innovators Launch GRAPHERGIA Project to Revolutionize Energy Harvesting in Textiles and Battery Technology	Press Release	https://graphergia.eu/2023/11/06/european-innovators-launch-graphergia-project-to-revolutionize-energy-harvesting-in-textiles-and-battery-technology/	107

Pending for EC approval

